

Chemosphere

Evidence linking cadmium and/or lead exposure to immunomodulatory effects in mammals based upon an adverse outcome pathways approach, and research perspectives --Manuscript Draft--

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Abstract:	<p>For decades, studies have shown how exposure to non-essential trace metals such as lead (Pb) and cadmium (Cd) impact wildlife. Ecoimmunotoxicology has emerged in the past two decades and focuses on the effects of pollutants on the immune system of free-ranging organisms. Adverse outcome pathways (AOPs) represent a conceptual approach to explore the mechanistic linkage between a molecular initiating event and adverse outcomes, at all biological levels of organisation. This paper proposes putative AOPs related to the effects of Cd, Pb, and the mixture Cd-Pb, on the immune system of mammals to address future questions in ecoimmunotoxicology. Molecular Initiating Events for both metals relate to entrance in cells through Ca²⁺ channels or bond to cell surfaces. Exposure to Cd, Pb and Cd-Pb share several similar Key Events (KEs), primarily an increase of oxidative stress (OS) in immune cells through production of reactive oxygen species. For both metals and the mixture, OS affects mitochondrial membranes, and induces apoptosis, ultimately decreasing immune cell number. Both metals affect innate immune system through nuclear factor kappa B (NF-κB) and mitogen-activated protein kinase (MAPK) inflammatory signalling pathways, leading to an upregulation of inflammatory markers and mediators. Adaptive immune system is affected by the exposure to both metals through a decrease of CD4⁺/CD8⁺ ratio and MHCII, an inactivation of TH1 and TH2 response, and an inhibition of the humoral response mediated by various Ig. Mixture effects of Cd-Pb are less documented resulting in a more speculative AOP, but synergic and antagonistic effects were identified. According to our AOPs, further research in ecoimmunotoxicology of metals in mammals should focus on KEs related to NF-κB/MAPK inflammatory signalling pathways, changes in CD4⁺/CD8⁺ ratio and MHCII complexes, and on AOs related to auto-immune disorders and on the effective increase of infection rate, particularly in case of exposure to metal mixtures.</p>
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Besançon, 09/23/2024

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Subject: *Submission of a manuscript to Chemosphere*

Dear Editor,

We are pleased to submit our manuscript titled “Adverse outcome pathways of trace metals (cadmium, lead) from molecular initiating events to immune dysfunctions in mammals”, which we would like to see published in *Chemosphere*.

Among the approaches used in ecotoxicology to study the cascade (from molecular to population or community levels) of toxic effects of pollutants, adverse outcome pathways (AOPs) appear as an innovative and useful concept that could improve the mechanistic understanding of the impacts of contaminants on organisms. A few reviews addressed the single effects of these metals on the immune systems of mammals but, to our knowledge, none built proper adverse outcome pathways or reviewed the mixture effects of these metals on mammals’ immune response. In this paper, we built three different adverse outcome pathways about the single and combined effects of cadmium and lead that lead to immune dysfunctions in mammals.

This manuscript gives new insights into how cadmium and lead exposure can modulate the immunocompetence of mammals using the AOPs framework. It allows us to identify clear research gaps in ecoimmunotoxicology. This work can serve current issues on pollution and pathogens interaction as well as guiding futures applied research and risk assessors.

We therefore think that this paper would be of interest to the readership of *Chemosphere*.

We propose below a list of potential reviewers for our article:

- Nynke Kramer: nynke.kramer@wur.nl
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- Rikke Poulsen: rikkepoulsen@uvic.ca

Thank you very much for considering our work.

With our best regards,

Cloe Hadjadji, on behalf of all co-authors.

1 **Evidence linking cadmium and/or lead exposure to immunomodulatory**
2 **effects in mammals based upon an adverse outcome pathways**
3 **approach, and research perspectives**

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11 **Abstract:** For decades, studies have shown how exposure to non-essential trace metals such as lead (Pb) and
12 cadmium (Cd) largely impact global wildlife. Ecoimmunotoxicology has emerged in the past two decades and
13 focuses on the effects of pollutants on the immune system of free-ranging organisms. Adverse outcome
14 pathways (AOPs) represent a conceptual approach to explore the mechanistic linkage between a molecular
15 initiating event and adverse outcomes, potentially at all biological levels of organisation. The present paper
16 proposes putative AOPs related to the effects of Cd, Pb, and the mixture Cd-Pb, on the immune system of
17 mammals to address future questions in ecoimmunotoxicology. Molecular Initiating Events for both metals
18 relate to entrance in cells through Ca²⁺ channels or bond to cell surfaces. Exposure to Cd, Pb and Cd-Pb share
19 several similar Key Events (KEs), primarily an increase of oxidative stress (OS) in immune cells through
20 production of reactive oxygen species. For both metals and the mixture, OS affects mitochondrial membranes,
21 and induces apoptosis, ultimately decreasing immune cell number. Both metals affect innate immune system
22 through nuclear factor kappa B (NF-κB) and mitogen-activated protein kinase (MAPK) inflammatory signalling
23 pathways, leading to an upregulation of inflammatory markers and mediators. Adaptive immune system is
24 also affected by the exposure to both metals though a decrease of CD4+/CD8+ ratio, a decrease of MHCII, an

25 inactivation of T_H1 and T_H2 response, and an inhibition of the humoral response mediated by various Ig.
26 Mixture effects of Cd-Pb are less documented resulting in a more speculative AOP, but potential synergic and
27 antagonistic effects were identified. According to our AOPs, further research in ecoimmunotoxicology of
28 metals in free-ranging mammals should focus on KEs related to NF- κ B/MAPK inflammatory signalling
29 pathways, changes in CD4+/CD8+ ratio and MHCII complexes, and on AOs related to auto-immune disorders
30 and on the effective increase of infection rate, particularly in case of exposure to metal mixtures.

31

Highlights:

- We built AOPs relevant to the effects of Cd and/or Pb on mammalian immune system
- MIEs involve entrance in cells through Ca^{2+} channels or binding to cell surfaces
- KEs involve oxidative stress, NF- κ B signalling pathways, changes in CD4+/CD8+ ratio
- AOs include immunodeficiency, auto-immunity, and potential increased infection rate
- Gaps in current knowledge and detailed research perspectives are provided

Manuscript Number: CHEM142088: Adverse outcome pathways of trace metals (cadmium, lead) from molecular initiating events to immune dysfunctions in mammals

Besançon, 20/12/2024

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Subject: Submission of the CHEM142088 revised manuscript

Dear Editor,

We are pleased to submit the revised version of our paper initially entitled “Adverse outcome pathways of trace metals (cadmium, lead) from molecular initiating events to immune dysfunctions in mammals”, which we would like to see published in Chemosphere. Please find hereafter the comments from Editors and Reviewers, and our responses. According to comments from the Reviewer 1, the title of the revised version would now be: “Evidence linking cadmium and/or lead exposure to immunomodulatory effects in mammals based upon an adverse outcome pathways approach, and research perspectives”.

We thank the reviewers for their comments and suggestions, that we have followed carefully, as you will see below. In bold are the comments of the reviewers, in normal font our responses. We believe that reviewers’ comments indeed greatly improved our manuscript, and we hope that it is now acceptable for publication in Chemosphere.

Thank you very much for considering our work.

With our best regards,

On behalf of co-authors of the revised version of the manuscript CHEM142088,

Cloé Hadjadji.

Reviewer #1:

After reading through, I'm somewhat puzzled about the purpose of this paper. In broad strokes, the content is consistent with the objectives laid out in the introduction - namely to "propose putative AOPs" and "to address future questions in stress ecology" - although arguably, the authors "pose future questions" rather than addressing those questions.

We understand the remark of the reviewer. Thus, we develop in the revised version a paragraph specific to our opinion about how the field of ecoimmunotoxicology of metals might be advanced. In the Introduction section, the objective of the present paper was stated as follows: "The present paper focusses on the effects of Cd and Pb on the immune system of mammals to propose putative AOPs to test more mechanistic hypotheses in ecoimmunotoxicology of metals and to address future questions in stress ecology (as other stressors than metals act on immunity)." We acknowledge that perspectives were not developed enough in the previous section, and that the objective of "addressing future questions" was not fully fulfilled. Now that it has been done in the revised version, it seems that the sentence above clearly states the purpose of the paper, and we thus would like to keep it as it was.

The authors conducted a literature review focused on immunomodulating effects of Cd and Pb exposure with the aim of developing hypothesized adverse outcome pathways. Notably, their approach ignores the first principle of AOP development - that AOPs are not chemical specific. Rather than focusing on general biological response to events like increased reactive oxygen species or inhibition of δ -ALAD activity, the authors outline highly overlapping, but nonetheless distinct AOPs for Cd, Pb, and a mixture of the two. Moreso than trying to develop chemically-agnostic generalized AOPs, it seems like the authors are using the AOP framework to organize an evidence map of the empirical results they found that potentially/plausibly link Cd or Pb exposure to immunodeficiency or immunostimulation. There is nothing fundamentally wrong with the latter, but I think the effort would be better portrayed as evidence mapping than AOP development.

We also understand the reviewer's remark. Our aim was not to develop AOPs as they indeed are, by definition, chemically-agnostic. Rather, we aimed at building what the reviewer calls an "evidence map" of the results published in the scientific literature about the mechanisms who link the exposure to Cd and Pb (or the mixture of both) to immunomodulatory effects in mammals. To do so, rather than a classical systematic literature review, we used the AOP approach as it allows to picture more mechanistically the relationships between exposure and effects. However, the field of ecoimmunotoxicology is relatively new, and thus we only found around 50 papers related to the issue. This prevented us to make true evidence mapping or to use the bibliometrics approach (as suggested by reviewer 2), as the latter is more appropriate to analyse a very large body of articles. The title of the revised version is now "Evidence linking cadmium

and/or lead exposure to immunomodulatory effects in mammals based upon an adverse outcome pathways approach, and research perspectives". This will prevent readers to think that we "developed" AOPs and understand more clearly that we used the AOP framework to address future research questions in the field of ecoimmunotoxicology. For the same reason, the titles of sections 3, 4 and 6 have been changed from "Development of an AOP for the effects of Cd on the immune system of mammals" towards "Evidence of the effects of Cd on the immune system of mammals based on an AOP framework".

If the goal were to develop AOPs, I would recommend that the authors populate information into the AOP-Wiki in accordance with OECD guidance and provide a full description of the key events and key event relationships (as available evidence allows) along with an overall evaluation of the level of support for the AOPs developed. Likewise, if the goal is AOP development, I would encourage the authors to focus more heavily on what is common to both Cd and Pb induced immunotoxicity and where the evidence is strongest across both stressors rather than on the margins or where the data are ambiguous.

As said before, our aim was not really to develop AOP but rather to use an AOP approach to sum up what is known about the immunomodulatory effects of Cd and/or Pb in mammals, and then to draw research perspectives in this field. However, we acknowledge that having an AOP related to Cd exposure, and one related to Pb exposure, without comparing what is common or different between the 2 might also be frustrating to the reader. Thus, we added a new graph in the revised version tackling this comparison. We however would like to keep each of the AOP (and related paragraphs) as they allow to explain in more details the mechanisms related to the exposure of each of the 2 metals.

In the latter half of the paper the authors describe some limitations and propose some next steps and broad questions that need to be addressed. However, much of this comes off as very broad generalizations and general calls that "we need to do this" but without any concrete or practical proposals for how to go about it.

For example, lines 235-237 - the authors propose that "...every aspect of the potential impacts of toxic metals on the immune system....should be investigated in the wild...." How in practice, or in any practical sense would this be achieved? Such a statement is rather meaningless without any way to address it. Much of what follows details the complexities but offers no solutions. It's simple to say organisms and ecosystems are complex and challenge our understanding. It is far more difficult (but far more helpful) to offer practical strategies to cope with these challenges. The section concluded with "there is a great need to develop more immune-related methods in wild animals to achieve the same level of precision than in labs or humans" - without a strategy for how to do it, this is little more than words to fill a page. Its like saying, world peace is desirable - a nice sentiment, with little value if you can't provide a plan for how to achieve it.

In the end, while there is some merit to the evidence mapping and some aspects of the discussion, the overall significance and potential impact of the work seems unclear - at least to this reader. More emphasis should be placed on what aspects of this work will drive the field forward.

As said before, we acknowledge this limitation in the present version, and the revised version should now fill this gap, to the best of our abilities and skills in this scientific field. To this end, the paragraph 6 entitled "Research perspectives from our AOPs and limitations" has been entirely rewritten and completed by much more precise recommendations for further research in the field. Consequently to the addition of the new paragraph 5 "Similarities and differences between Cd and Pb effects on the immune system of mammals based on an AOP framework", the new paragraph dealing with research perspectives is numbered 7 and entitled "Gaps in current knowledge and research perspectives". Given that it has been completely rewritten, keeping the track changes made it unreadable and in this paragraph only, track changes have not been kept in the revised version.

1. Highlight bullet 2 - AOPs are not chemical specific. Strictly speaking, there are no AOPs for Cd or Pb - rather AOPs that are relevant to effects of Cd or Pb

Corrected: The new highlight bullet 2 becomes "We built AOPs relevant to the effects of Cd and/or Pb on mammalian immune system" in the revised version.

2. Highlight bullet 5 - Suggest deleting "potential" from "potential increased infection rates"

Here, we are afraid not to be in agreement with the reviewer. From our literature review, it appears that immunodeficiencies and auto-immunity issues in mammals exposed to Cd and/or Pb have been demonstrated, while there are only hypotheses or presumptions about the modulation of infection rates. Therefore, we would like to keep this highlight as it is in the present version.

3. Line 6 - consider "contrary" rather than "contrarily"

Done (line 6).

4. Lines 10-11. "...the proportion of the total concentration of a chemical this is actually taken up from the environment..." - this is not a very precise definition of bioavailability. Consider revision.

We agree that this definition is simpler than the full one, detailing the 3 components (environmental availability, environmental bioavailability, and toxicological bioavailability) of bioavailability, as described in papers such as the ones from Lanno et al. 2004 or Naidu et al. 2008 that we cite in this very sentence). However, it seems to us that, in the present paper which is not specifically related to bioavailability issues, this simple and concise definition is enough. Therefore, we would prefer keeping this sentence as it is in the present version.

5. Lines 72-73. E.AOP.portal and AOP-wiki are simply two ways of accessing the same AOP information - not really separate data sources. Effectopedia is no longer maintained. AOP Xplorer has limited content that was derived from an obsolete version of the AOP-Wiki. With this in mind, the AOP-Wiki should be cited as the primary source of information.

We removed the other databases and cited only the AOP-Wiki with a link to the website.

6. Line 75. Table 2 - consider adding the URL for the AOP-Wiki (aopwiki.org) to the table 2 legend. Likewise, the terminology generally used is Event ID, not "code".

The link to the AOP-Wiki has been given previously (line 78). According to the reviewer's request, we changed "code" for "Event ID" when it appeared in the paper (example: line 82).

7. Lines 118-119. How is this variation in outcome depending on the exposure duration represented in the AOPs you've developed? Perhaps the acute versus chronic nature of the different paths should be represented graphically in Figure 2. As it is difficult to figure this clearly on the Figure 2, we added an asterisk reporting to a sentence under the figure explaining this.

8. Figure 2 versus Figure 3. There are many similarities in the pathways for Cd and Pb depicted. Are the differences fundamental biological differences in how organisms respond to these two different metals (which would seem to require some difference in MIEs) or do these just reflect the body of evidence and which pathway(s) have been studied in relation to each. Are they truly distinct, or is it more or less a common response that is perhaps better studied with one metal versus the other? Is it only Pb that affects -ALA-D? Does that inhibition fundamentally change the impact of ROS.

Regarding immunomodulatory effects of the exposure to Cd and/or Pb, we are not aware that experiments have been conducted, in the same conditions, to compare the immunotoxicological mechanisms of Cd and Pb. Some mechanisms like the inhibition of the ALA-D are clearly specific to the exposure to Pb but while some more global immune responses like tissue inflammation related to cytokine production within the NF- κ B signaling pathway are common to the exposure to Cd or Pb. This is now illustrated by a new paragraph (section 5 in the revised version) and a new Figure (numbered 4 in the revised version), which shows, according to one of the Reviewer's 1 comment, the mechanisms common to the exposure to Cd or Pb. However, we cannot assure that some differences between immune mechanisms under exposure to Cd or Pb are not also related to a lack of research. We stated this limitation in the text of this new paragraph 5. There is no information, to our knowledge, about the actual impact of the inhibition of the ALA-D on the overall ROS production under exposure to Pb.

9. Lines 206-207. "Overall Cd and Pb produce similar effects...." - this raises the question of whether the underlying pathways and processes really differ for the two metals (and thus represent distinct AOPs). Rather than presenting separate AOPs for Cd, Pb, and a mixture of the two (which likely just reflect what different published studies focused on), it would be more helpful to build a single AOP relevant to all three, that is built on the strongest and most consistent evidence, regardless of the stressor involved.

We believe that our new Figure 4 and the text accompanying it answer this comment. We however would prefer keeping the AOPs specific to the exposure to Cd and to Pb because many subtle differences (e.g. in the cytokines and immunoglobulins mobilized in the immune responses) differ among metals. Similarly, we would prefer keeping a Figure about the immune responses to the exposure to the mixture Cd-Pb as much less is known in this area.

10. Line 238. Consider highlighting the potential biomarkers with something like a different font type or a symbol in addition to the different colors. Readers accessing the article in black and white (and potentially color blind readers) would not be able to distinguish the colors being referenced.

Done, we added black stars in every figures to facilitate the comprehension of the readers.

11. Line 280. Wouldn't the large cell to cell variability even among adjacent cells argue that single-cell or small population investigations could be misleading, and that it is important to survey a large population of cells to get an overall sense of a tissue-level response?

This is indeed an interesting hypothesis but to our knowledge this has not been assessed yet; therefore, we cannot easily advice about this and we would prefer just attracting the interest of readers on this cell to cell variability.

12. Line 287. Suggest "best of our knowledge..." instead of "...best of your knowledge...."

Done (line 314).

Reviewer #2:

This manuscript summarized recent advances in the negative effects of Cd and Pb on the mammalian immune system, with a focus on adverse outcome pathways. The manuscript is well-written. I only have a few questions for the author's concern.

1), In the "Introduction", it should be explained why only mammals are focused on. As we all know, fish are also a valuable model for building AOP.

We acknowledge that other animal models are suitable for studying the impacts of metals on the immune system and/or for building AOPs. However, we focused on mammals (and particularly terrestrial ones) because reviews have recently been published on immune toxicity of metals or contaminants including metals in fish (Lee et al., 2023, *Environmental Research* 236: 116600; Lee et al., 2019, *Environmental Toxicology and Pharmacology* 68: 101-108), birds (Vallverdu et al., 2019, *Science of the Total Environment* 689: 505–515) and marine mammals (Desforges et al., 2016, *Environment International* 86: 126–139). We did not find any recent review (based or not on the AOP framework) for the immunotoxicity of terrestrial mammals. Moreover, this is the model we are most experienced with, and immune systems and mechanisms underlying the impacts of metals among vertebrates are relatively different, which would have made a much too large paper if we had reviewed immunotoxicity of metals on several vertebrates. This has been stated in the Introduction of the revised version (line 58-61).

2), Why focus on these two heavy metals? The significance should be clarified.

Cadmium and lead are, with arsenic and mercury, among the 10 chemicals or groups of chemicals of major public health concern at a global scale (World Health Organization 2024). We however focus here on Cd and Pb only as they are more relevant than As or Hg to terrestrial mammals in terms of exposure, and to keep the present article at a reasonable size. This has been added at the end of the Introduction section in the present revised version (line 61-64).

3), Bibliometrics is an emerging and important tool for writing Review. It must be used in this topic.

Bibliometric analysis is indeed an increasingly popular and a rigorous method for reviewing the literature, but this tool is more dedicated to explore and analyze large volumes of scientific data (Donthu et al., 2021, *Journal of Business Research* 133: 285–296). This approach offers the opportunity to analyse largely populated research domains by examining influential ties in terms of key contributions, prolific authors, on-topic journals and chronological evolutions (Marzi et al. 2024, *International Journal of Management Reviews* 1-23). In the present case, where around 50 papers were published about the impacts of cadmium and/or lead on the immune system of terrestrial mammals, it seemed to us that this framework was not appropriate. Additionally, the AOP framework allowed to work more on mechanistic aspects of Cd/Pb immunotoxicity. Therefore, we would prefer declining the suggestion of the Reviewer to use the bibliometric approach for the present paper.

Graphical abstract:

1 **1. Introduction**

2 Wildlife has been threatened for decades by several stressors from anthropogenic activities, which leads
3 to the sixth mass extinction (Birnie-Gauvin et al., 2017; Ceballos et al., 2017) and makes conservation of the
4 biodiversity one of the main issues of the century. Stressors are coming from many sources, including the
5 exposure to different kinds of pollutants such as non-essential trace metals (TMs) (for readability purpose,
6 this acronym and other used in the present paper are presented in **Table 1**). Contrary to essential elements
7 that have important physiological functions in organisms, metals such as cadmium (Cd) or lead (Pb) are non-
8 essential elements to vertebrates since they are not known to have any biological function (Aras and Ataman,
9 2007). Transfer of these toxic metals from the environment to the organisms depends on several parameters
10 regulating their bioavailability (Lanno et al., 2004), defined as the proportion of the total concentration of a
11 chemical that is actually taken up from the environment (Naidu et al., 2008). Toxicological bioavailability refers
12 to the proportion of the concentration taken up that reaches toxicological targets (e.g., cells, tissues, organs)
13 through the circulatory system, subsequently causing a biological response (Lanno et al., 2004). Historically,
14 studies on TMs have mainly focused on accumulation in tissues and effects on classical ecotoxicological
15 endpoints (mortality, reproduction outputs, histopathology, biochemical, physiological disorders...) while
16 unconventional endpoints, such as impacts on the immune system or behaviour, have attracted more
17 attention only recently. Ecoimmunotoxicology refers to the understanding of the interactions between
18 exposure to pollutants, immune cells and the “delicate interactions associated with homeostasis mediated
19 by the immune system” (Tryphonas, 2005; Gallucci et al., 2020).

20 **Table 1.**

21 Exposure to non-essential TMs at toxic levels can affect the immune system through an up-regulation
22 (immunoactivation) or a down-regulation (immunodeficiency), both referring to immunomodulation (Zelikoff
23 et al., 1994; Devalloir et al., 2023). Immunodeficiency is defined as the decrease in effectiveness of the
24 immune response (Gallucci et al., 2020) while immunostimulation refers to the enhancement of the defensive
25 response, that can lead to auto-immune dysfunction or overall immune hypersensitivity (Luster and
26 Gerberick, 2010; McKee and Fontenot, 2016; Gallucci et al., 2020). These immunomodulation processes

27 mediated by toxic metals impact both innate and adaptive responses by unsettling the balanced mechanisms
28 of immune cell regulation (Tersago et al., 2004; Ebrahimi et al., 2020). Immunomodulation is also linked to a
29 myriad of external factors and stressors such as food shortage, life stage, or exposure to pathogens (Jackson
30 et al., 2009; Poulsen and Escher, 2012). Toxic effects also vary with species, sex, type (chronic or acute) and
31 route (ingestion, inhalation, dermal contact) of exposure (Gallucci et al., 2020). Immune cell dysfunction can
32 occur through ionic substitution of toxic metals due to similar affinity to receptors on organic compounds,
33 such as Cd^{2+} crossing Ca^{2+} channels (Choong et al., 2014). The main mechanism responsible for immune cell
34 damages is related to the toxicological impact of reactive oxygen species (ROS) including immune cell
35 membrane degradation (e.g., lipopolyperoxydation, Gera et al., 2015). Cadmium and Pb also have the ability
36 to up- or down- regulate inflammatory mediators and markers (cytokines, chemokines...), which can directly
37 modify the immune response (Ebrahimi et al., 2020; Devalloir et al., 2023). Cadmium and Pb can thus induce
38 differential effects on cytokine production through different signalling pathways (Thévenod and Lee, 2015).
39 For example, an increase of the pro-inflammatory response (TNF- α) has been shown in wood mice living near
40 a former smelter site contaminated by high Cd and Pb levels (Devalloir et al., 2023).

41 Since the emergence and the development of ecotoxicology in the 60's, the discipline has evolved from a
42 relatively descriptive field to a much more mechanistic, hypothesis-based science. It aims at providing both a
43 better understanding of how pollutants can affect organisms at various spatial, temporal, and biological
44 organisation scales, and an improvement of risk assessment of chemicals released into the environment.
45 Among the approaches used in ecotoxicology to study the cascade (from molecular to population or
46 community levels) toxic effects of pollutants, adverse outcome pathways (AOPs) appeared as an innovative
47 and useful concept that could improve mechanistic approaches, here in ecoimmunotoxicology (Tryphonas,
48 2005; Baudiffier et al., 2024). Adverse outcome pathways represent a conceptual framework that highlights
49 existing knowledge linking a molecular initiating event (MIE) induced by a given toxic chemical to an adverse
50 outcome (AO) at multiple levels of biological organisation (Ankley et al., 2010). An AOP represents a
51 succession of key events (KEs) that can take various forms and depend on the information available. Molecular
52 initiating events are located at the molecular level and can be defined as "the initial points of chemical-

53 biological interaction within the organism” (Figure 1, Vinken et al., 2017). The relationship(s) between the
54 different events can be causal, mechanistic, inferential or correlation-based (Ankley et al., 2010).

55 **Figure 1.**

56 The present paper focusses on the effects of Cd and Pb on the immune system of mammals to propose
57 putative AOPs to test more mechanistic hypotheses in ecoimmunotoxicology of metals and to address future
58 questions in stress ecology (as other stressors than metals act on immunity) and ecotoxicology of free-ranging
59 mammals. Here, we focus on terrestrial mammals because reviews have recently been published on immune
60 toxicity of metals (or contaminants including metals) in fish (Lee et al., 2023, 2019), birds (Vallverdú-Coll et
61 al., 2019) and marine mammals (Desforges et al., 2016). All arsenic (As), Cd, Pb, and mercury (Hg) belong to
62 the 10 chemicals or groups of chemicals of major public health concern at a global scale (World Health
63 Organization, 2024). We however focus here on Cd and Pb only as they are more relevant than As or Hg to
64 terrestrial mammals in terms of exposure, and to keep the present article at a reasonable size. We based the
65 construction of our AOPs on reviewing the literature in the area, our own experience in ecoimmunotoxicology,
66 and different interactive databases related to AOPs. These databases provide open-source interfaces to
67 deposit AOPs, which facilitates the sharing of AOP knowledge and collaborative work (reviewed in Vinken et
68 al., 2017).

69 **2. Materials and Methods**

70 The articles presented in this paper have been selected according to the PRISMA statement (Moher et al.,
71 2009). Literature search for study cases on terrestrial mammals was performed with Web of Sciences (June
72 2023) by using the following keywords, alone or in combination, full or truncated: immune system, immunity,
73 oxidative stress, AOPs/Adverse outcomes pathways, biomarkers, mammals (wild or captive), metals/heavy
74 metals, Pb/Lead, Cd/Cadmium, mixture effects. We also included other review articles about AOPs,
75 immunology and immunotoxicity in mammals. We ended up with 123 articles after the identification phase
76 and then selected the most pertinent articles based on their title and abstract (screening phase). After the
77 eligibility phase, we finally kept 51 articles, that were included in our synthesis. After reviewing the literature
78 and building pre-AOPs, we used the AOP-wiki interactive databases (<https://aopwiki.org/>, Vinken et al., 2017)

79 to expand our AOPs and link them to the existing knowledge. Each KE identified in the literature was
80 associated with a specific KE from AOP-wiki when it existed (Table 2). The Event ID of each KE was then added
81 in our AOPs (see Figures). General knowledge (i.e., introduction, information about TMs) and perspectives
82 were based on other bibliographic searches and on our experience.

83 **Table 2.**

84 **3. Evidence of the effects of Cd on the immune system of mammals based on an AOP** 85 **framework**

86 Cadmium in the environment comes from both natural and anthropogenic sources. Primary natural source
87 of Cd is related to geological processes, such as volcanic activity (Doelsch et al., 2006). Its occurrence is natural
88 in all types of soils and minerals, e.g., sulfate, sulfide, carbonate... (Kabata-Pendias, 2010). Anthropogenic
89 sources of Cd include mining, smelting activity, transport, burial of nickel-Cd batteries, manufacturing, and
90 pesticides spreading (Hosseini-Khannazer et al., 2020). Main routes of exposure to Cd in mammals are through
91 air, water, and food intake. Cadmium enters the body *via* the respiratory and the gastrointestinal tract (Mirkov
92 et al., 2021). It is then transported into the blood, bound to some proteins such as albumin (Mirkov et al.,
93 2021) and brought to the organs where it accumulates. Overall, all the organs are targeted by Cd but its
94 accumulation is always higher in the liver and kidneys (Sarkar et al., 2013). Cells and tissues exposed to Cd
95 are mainly damaged by oxidative stress, even if reactive oxygen species (ROS) are not directly produced by
96 Cd. Reactive oxygen species are naturally produced during oxygen metabolism and are essential for cell
97 signalling and homeostasis. However, high amounts of ROS disrupt cell functioning, including immune cells,
98 and produce several adverse effects. Cadmium is considered as an immunotoxic inhibitor, influencing both
99 innate and adaptive immune responses, which can alter immune cells functions (Mirkov et al., 2021). Major
100 effects of Cd on the immune system reported in the literature are: (1) Cd-dependent apoptosis, (2) variations
101 in immune cells activation and differentiation, and (3) enhancement of inflammatory responses in immune
102 cells by up- and down-regulation of cytokines production (Genchi et al., 2020; Wang et al., 2021).

103 We identified two main MIEs for Cd, which result in significant AOs on the immune system (Figure 2). The
104 first one is linked to the chemical properties of Cd as, under its ionic form Cd²⁺, it is known to interfere with

105 essential metal ions involved in biological functions of organisms (Thévenod and Lee, 2015). Thus, Cd²⁺ can
106 block Ca²⁺ channels because of their thiol group affinity. It induces a major disturbance of cellular homeostasis
107 and affects protein structure. The second MIE is the binding of Cd on the cell surface (Choong et al., 2014).
108 Both MIEs are activating a reaction cascade of several KEs linked to immune dysfunctions.

109 The first step of this cascade is the induction of ROS production. Increase in oxidative stress affects
110 mitochondrial membranes, which plays a major role in mitochondrial ROS formation, and leads to apoptosis
111 (Genchi et al., 2020; Wang et al., 2021). Reactive oxygen species increase is responsible for the activation of
112 the NF-κB pathway, which is in turn linked to the increase of the production of the pro-inflammatory cytokines
113 IL-1b, IL-6 and TNF-α (Wang et al., 2021) and of some chemokines (IL-8, MIP-2). Enhancement of both IL-6
114 and TNF-α in neutrophils (i.e., the most abundant type of granulocytes) leads to potential indirect effects of
115 Cd on haematopoiesis because these cytokines are regulators of this mechanism (Ulich et al., 1989). It can
116 indicate a hypersensitive reaction. Bioassays using macrophages from murine cells line RAW 264.7 exposed
117 to Cd concentrations showed an increase in the pro-inflammatory cytokine IL-1β associated with an inhibition
118 of IL-6 and IL-10 (Riemschneider et al., 2015). Because of this modulation, a potential hyper-reactivity of
119 macrophages can occur, which could lead to autoimmune disorder in mammals. In addition, Jung and Oh
120 (2019) reported an increase of TNF-α 6h after an exposure to Cd, which would indicate a response from
121 macrophages to Cd toxicity. However, 18h after the exposure, a decrease in TNF-α was associated with
122 apoptosis in RAW 264.7 (So et al., 2018). These results suggest that Cd immunotoxicity varies according to
123 exposure time, resulting in a hyperactivation of the immune system during short-term exposure while long-
124 term exposure results in immunodeficiency.

125 During the regulation of oxidative stress balance, the increase of glutathione (GSH) can cause a decrease
126 in CD4+/CD8+ ratio (CD: cluster of differentiation), with a decrease of CD4+ (helper T-cells) and an increase
127 of CD8+ (cytotoxic T-cells; Devalloir et al., submitted). Moreover, a decrease in CD4+ can be linked to a
128 diminution of IL-2 and IFN-γ production (Pathak and Khandelwal, 2009). A decrease in IL-2, the main factor
129 for proliferation of activated T-cells, has been observed in mouse splenic cells after Cd exposure (Pathak and
130 Khandelwal, 2009). These results show that Cd participates to the overall inactivation and immunodeficiency
131 of the adaptive immune response in mammals. In addition, IFN-γ can be both enhanced or inhibited by Cd

132 exposure (Krocova et al., 2000; Turley et al., 2019), depending on the dose and time-exposure. Turley et al.
133 (2019) reported an enhancement of IFN- γ during low-dose Cd exposure (32 ppm in drinking water for 10 days)
134 without significantly affecting T-cell polarization in rats. On the contrary, a decrease of IFN- γ has been
135 reported in T-cells when exposed to higher Cd concentrations (Krocova et al., 2000).

136 Reactive oxygen species production also promotes the expression of some pro-inflammatory cytokines
137 such as IL-1b, IL-6 and TNF- α and inhibits anti-inflammatory cytokines such as IL-10 in macrophages (Wang et
138 al., 2021). The overexpression of IL-1b, IL-6 and TNF- α as well as the inhibition of IL-10 can result in hyper-
139 inflammation, auto immune disorders and in rare cases, cancer (Thévenod and Lee, 2015). Overall, a
140 dysregulation in cytokine production can affect the activation of TH1, Th2 or TH17 (Devalloir, 2023). In
141 addition, the binding of Cd on the cell surface induces a decrease of the expression of the major
142 histocompatibility complex class 2 (MCHII) on B-cells, which could affect the presentation of pathogens to
143 antigen presenting cells and decrease the effectiveness of the immune system in response to pathogens.
144 Antibody production is also directly affected by Cd exposure. In the spleen, B-cell antibody responses differ
145 with dose, class of antigen (IgG, IgM), antigen type (T-cell independent, T-cell dependent) and exposure
146 duration (Fujimaki et al., 1982). A decrease in IgE production has been highlighted after Cd exposure in
147 humans (Wang et al., 2021). Cadmium exposure also induces the transformation of IgE antibodies into IgG
148 produced by B lymphocytes in humans (Marth et al., 2001), indicating an impairment of the cell activation
149 initiation during cytotoxic signals (Wang et al., 2021).

150

151 **Figure 2.**

152 **4. Evidence of the effects of Pb on the immune system of mammals based on an AOP**
153 **framework**

154 Lead is a naturally occurring but potentially harmful element, present at high concentrations in the
155 environment mainly because of anthropogenic sources. This element is naturally present in the earth crust at
156 very low concentration and small amount are released in the environment due to natural processes as rocks
157 weathering (Pattee and Pain, 2002). Regarding anthropogenic sources, Pb is used in paints, pesticides,
158 gasoline, batteries, and other emissions that can come from smelting activity and industry (Wani et al., 2015).
159 Main routes of exposure in mammals are through air and food intake, where it can be absorbed by respiratory
160 and digestive tracts (Balali-Mood et al., 2021). Accumulation in several organs generate multiple adverse
161 effects such as nervous system disorders (e.g., saturnism), kidney and liver alteration, anaemia, or learning
162 disorders in children (Ebrahimi et al., 2020). The oxidant-antioxidant balance system can be disturbed by Pb
163 exposure, which can lead to inflammatory responses in organs (Balali-Mood et al., 2021). Lead also is
164 considered as an immunotoxic inhibitor, influencing both innate and adaptive immune responses that can
165 alter all immune cells (Metryka et al., 2018). The major effects of Pb on the immune system reported in the
166 literature are (1) the enhancement of anti- and pro-inflammatory responses, (2) depression of humoral
167 immunity, and (3) immune cell damage at high Pb concentration.

168 Lead exposure, either chronic or acute, can induce two potential MIEs, that result in severe AOs on the
169 functioning of the immune system. First, the inhibition of δ -aminolaevulinic acid dehydratase (δ -ALA-D) by Pb
170 can lead to a rapid oxidizing of δ -ALA. Quantification of δ -ALA-D has long been used as a biomarker of Pb
171 exposure (Rocha et al., 2012). However, its use as a biomarker of Pb exposure has to be cautious because
172 modulation of δ -ALA-D can occur after an exposure to other metals. When δ -ALA-D oxidation occurs, it
173 induces a production of free radicals including ROS, leading to oxidative stress (Lopes et al., 2016). Second,
174 Pb can bind to the cell surface to oxygen compounds due to its chemical properties. Both MIEs are activating
175 a reaction cascade of several KEs linked to immune responses dysfunctions (Figure 3).

176 Innate and adaptive immune responses are both impacted by a chronic or acute Pb exposure, by producing
177 ROS, modulating cytokines production, and T_H1/T_H2 polarisation. The induction of ROS production promotes
178 or suppresses the expression of a few cytokines. Iavicoli et al. (2006) reported an increase of IL-4 and a
179 decrease of IL-2 and IFN- γ production in mice exposed to high Pb level. In comparison, low-dose Pb exposure
180 induces a decrease in IL-4, and an increase of IL-2 and IFN- γ , meaning that immune response modulation
181 might be not linear (Iavicoli et al., 2006). These responses differently affect T_H1 and T_H2 polarisation and
182 humoral responses. High Pb levels could cause an impairment of cytotoxic signalling (T_H1) while low-dose Pb
183 affects the coordination of helper T-cell response (T_H2).

184 Studies also highlighted an increase of three pro-inflammatory cytokines, IL-1 β , TNF- α and IL-6, after an
185 exposure to Pb (Fenga et al., 2017), which could promote auto-immune damage. However, antioxidant
186 activation associated with Pb exposure, in response to oxidative stress, modified pro-inflammatory responses
187 by decreasing IL-1 β , TNF- α and IL-6. Furthermore, synergistic effect between Pb and lipopolysaccharides (i.e.,
188 LPS; an inducer of inflammatory response in organisms) has been demonstrated in the literature (Cheng et
189 al., 2009). LPS-induced mortality under Pb exposure has been observed in animal studies (Dentener et al.,
190 1989) and could be due to the tremendous release of TNF- α by different cells including both T and B
191 lymphocytes, macrophages, and monocytes. In human macrophages, *in vitro* stimulation by LPS showed a
192 surface TNF- α expression on over 50% of the cells after 24h. IL-8 gene expression is also enhanced by Pb
193 exposure when associated with p42/44 MAPK in human (Lin et al., 2015). Indeed, p42/44 MAPK has been
194 observed to activate IL-8 gene expression (Metryka et al., 2018).

195 Lead also causes a decline in humoral immunity by affecting both T_H1 and T_H2, which may increase host
196 vulnerability to bacterial and virus infections (Hemphill et al., 1971; Gainer, 1974; Luster et al., 1978). Lead
197 affects humoral immune response by reducing IgA and IgG production, which can induce inflammatory
198 diseases and cancers as long-term AOs (Anetor et al., 2008). Naïve CD4⁺ exposed to Pb will preferentially
199 differentiate in T_H2 and lead to the inhibition of T_H1 cell growth. This results in a decrease of IFN- γ and IgG₂
200 with an increase of IL-4, IgE, and IgG₄. Mice exposed to Pb and infected by *Listeria monocytogenes* showed
201 significant reduction in the CD4⁺ and CD8⁺ production (Dyatlov and Lawrence, 2002).

202

203 **Figure 3.**

204 **5. Similarities and differences between Cd and Pb effects on the immune system of mammals**
205 **based on an AOP framework**

206 Overall, Cd and Pb produce similar effects in vertebrates with outcomes resulting either
207 immunostimulation or immunodeficiency. Here, we propose a single AOP (Figure 4) presenting mechanisms
208 and pathways common to the exposure to both trace metals. To our knowledge, no experiments have been
209 conducted with the very same conditions to directly compare the immunotoxicological effect of Cd and Pb.
210 This means that we cannot be sure whether the differences in the immunomodulatory effects of the exposure
211 to Cd or Pb are actual differences in the underlying mechanisms or if this is related to a lack of research.

212 Concerning the innate system, common mechanisms include tissue inflammation related to the increased
213 production of pro-inflammatory cytokines within the NF- κ B signalling pathway and a reduction of
214 phagocytosis activity. In both cases, cytokine concentrations are modulated either up or down, leading to an
215 increased inflammation or an impaired signalling of the immune response. Concerning the adaptive response,
216 both trace metals affect the expression of MHCII and produce a decrease of the CD4+/CD8+ ratio, leading to
217 an inhibition of immunoglobulin production and an impairment of Th1 and Th2 response. These various
218 common pathways all lead to three main adverse effects such as immunostimulation, potential auto-immune
219 disorder/damage, immunodeficiency leading to potential increase infection rate, and in some cases even
220 cancer.

221 Differences in immunomodulatory effects of the exposure to Cd or Pb rely mainly on one feature specific
222 to Pb (Inhibition of the δ aminolaevulinic acid dehydratase, ALA-D) and differences in cytokines mobilised
223 through exposure to Cd or Pb (see Figures 2 and 3, and text below). The inhibition of ALA-D increases oxidative
224 stress in cells (Rocha et al., 2012) but we did not find to what extent this contributes to the overall increase
225 of oxidative stress related to the exposure to Pb. Cytokines and chemokines are modulated by the exposure
226 to Cd or Pb but according to previous studies, most of them are different for each metal indicating that
227 different pathways of the immune response are involved. For example, the extra activation of NF- κ B leads to
228 increased IL-8 and MIP-2 in the case of Cd exposure while an increase of IL-4 is reported in the case of Pb

229 exposure (Iavicoli et al., 2006; Wang et al., 2021). In the case of immunoglobulin production, studies showed
230 an inhibition of IgE and an inhibition of IgA and IgG in the case of Cd and Pb, respectively (Anetor et al., 2008;
231 Wang et al., 2021).

232 **Figure 4.**

233 **6. Evidence of the effects of a Cd-Pb mixture on the immune system of mammals based on** 234 **an AOP framework**

235 In the environment, organisms are generally exposed to a mixture of contaminants rather than to a single
236 trace metal. These multiple exposures can be detrimental to wild vertebrates even if contaminants are
237 present at low concentrations. This concept is called “cocktail effect” or “mixture toxicity” (Beyer et al., 2014).
238 Ecotoxicological studies have mainly been performed through a chemical-by-chemical approach of exposure,
239 while wildlife are exposed to “dynamic chemical mixtures” through their life (Morrissey et al., 2023). It exists
240 only a few papers that relate mixture effects of trace metal elements (Cd, Pb) on the immune system. Thus,
241 little is known about their additive, synergetic and/or antagonistic effects on the immune system of
242 vertebrates. Synergetic and antagonistic effects are the results of the competition among metals for organic
243 and inorganic ligands during accumulation and uptake (Altenburger et al., 2003; Belden et al., 2007; Balistrieri
244 and Mebane, 2014). It has been shown that Cd-Pb mixture can enhance the production of white blood cells
245 in mice, indicating the activation of the immune system in response to the exposure (Cobbina et al., 2015). In
246 addition, these authors found that the exposure to a mixture result in a global antagonistic effect, in
247 comparison to their individual toxic effect. One hypothesis could be that Cd and Pb both produce thiols such
248 as GSH, enabling a protection of the cell from their toxicity. However, other antioxidant markers (superoxide
249 dismutase, glutathione peroxidase) were lower when mice were exposed to a Cd and Pb mixture, potentially
250 creating higher oxidative stress in immune cells. Another study in male rat showed that the exposure to a
251 mixture of eight trace metals, including Cd and Pb, induces a suppression of both humoral and cell-mediated
252 immune response (Jadhav et al., 2007). Fortier et al. (2008) depicted a non-significant effect of the Cd-Pb
253 mixture in human leucocytes (viability and apoptosis proportion). These few studies provide different
254 conclusions, suggesting that a variety of pathways could be involved in the response to Cd-Pb mixture.

255 However, we still lack information about how cytokines signalling, T_H1/T_H2 polarization of B-cells and antibody
256 production could be modulated by this mixture. Here, we propose a potential AOP for Cd-Pb mixture on the
257 immune system of mammals with potential additive effects or synergetic and antagonistic interactions (Figure
258 5), based on the few studies presented earlier as well as on hypotheses and deductions from our single-
259 chemical AOPs (Figures 2, 3 and 4).
260

261 **Figure 5.**

262 **7. Gaps in current knowledge and research perspectives**

263 In the present article, we built putative AOPs depicting the cascade effects of Cd and Pb alone, and in
264 combination, on the immune system of mammals. We identified several pathways that could lead to immune
265 dysfunctions in mammals. However, despite identifying links between contaminants, MIEs, KEs and AOs using
266 the existing knowledge, how the different cascades of reactions occur in wild organisms, and what adverse
267 outcomes arise at various levels of biological organisation remain uncertain in wildlife since most of the work
268 has been done in lab animals. To fill this gap, we identified several biomarkers indicated in bright pink boxes
269 (and indicated by an asterisk) in Figures 2 to 6, and develop hereinafter the research priority identified from
270 these putative AOPs, the literature and our own experience in immunotoxicity of metals in free-ranging small
271 mammals (Devalloir et al., 2023; Powolny et al., 2023; ongoing research).

272 One of the primary aspects to consider, common to both Cd and Pb exposure, relies upon their impacts
273 through NF- κ B. This family of inducible transcription factors regulates multiple aspects of innate and adaptive
274 immune functions and is a pivotal mediator of inflammatory responses (Liu et al., 2017). NF- κ B induces
275 several functions in innate immune cells, including maturation of dendritic cells, activation and differentiation
276 of inflammatory T cells, polarization of macrophages and their production of pro-inflammatory
277 cytokines/chemokines, and recruitment of and anti-apoptotic effect on neutrophils. These cells express
278 pattern-recognition receptors that detect various microbial components (so-called pathogen-associated
279 molecules patterns, PAMPs) as well as molecules released by necrotic cells and damaged tissues (co-called
280 damage-associated molecular patterns, DAMPs). Thus, a disruption of NF- κ B by contaminants (here Cd or Pb)
281 could alter these functions and might lead to a lower ability of the innate immune system to fight against
282 pathogens. NF- κ B also exerts a central role in mediating T cell receptors signalling and naive T-cell activation,
283 which is an important component of the adaptive immune system. Deregulation of NF- κ B activation can cause
284 aberrant T-cell activation, which might lead to associated autoimmune and inflammatory responses.
285 Inflammation is a protective response of the host to infections and tissue damages and is normally beneficial
286 and resolved in a timely manner. Given that wild rodents have been shown to be particularly exposed to
287 infections, deregulation of NF- κ B activation by metals might be particularly harmful to wild animals, both by

288 lowering their ability to control pathogenic infections and through excessive or long-lasting tissue damages,
289 ultimately leading to acute or chronic inflammatory diseases (Liu et al., 2017). Studying this pathway,
290 especially in free-ranging wildlife, is however difficult due to the complexity of the activation of NF- κ B, which
291 involves two major pathways (canonical and non-canonical) related to different signalling mechanisms. The
292 first pathway responds to diverse stimuli including ligands of various cytokine receptors, pattern-recognition
293 receptors (PRRs), TNF receptor (TNFR) superfamily, B and T cell receptors. In contrast, the non-canonical
294 pathway selectively responds to a specific group of stimuli, including ligands of a subset of TNFR superfamily
295 members (Liu et al., 2017). Furthermore, the activity of NF- κ B depends on three layers of regulation. A first
296 layer refers to the dynamic nature of the NF- κ B system, which is never static and is schematically under 4
297 forms of activity (OFF, low- and high-ON, and constitutively active). In “OFF” state, the NF- κ B activity is usually
298 too low to be reliably detected (Meier-Soelch et al., 2021). Constitutively active state refers to significant NF-
299 κ B activity found in specific cells such as Sertoli cells, B cells, hair follicle cells and neurons, making it difficult
300 to be studied in wildlife. “Low ON” state refers to a continuous low-grade activation that occurs in situations
301 of smoldering inflammation or in tumour microenvironment, and “high ON” state is a fast and transient
302 activation in response to proinflammatory triggers. Another layer of regulation is related to the gene specific
303 recruitment of NF- κ B and a third one involves a remarkable cell to cell variability, with cells having low NF- κ B
304 activity while adjacent cells exhibit high activity and strong activation of NF- κ B target genes (Meier-Soelch et
305 al., 2021). These authors therefore warn that (cell) population-based assays can be potentially misleading.
306 The NF- κ B activation rarely occurs in isolation and frequently other stress pathways such as p38 mitogen-
307 activated protein kinases (p38 MAPKs), c-Jun N-terminal kinases (JNKs) or JAK-STAT are activated in parallel.
308 As all have been shown to be involved in metal-related toxicity in human or lab-animal models (but not in
309 AOP framework to the best of our knowledge), they are also good candidate models to be further studied in
310 metal immunotoxicology.

311 Studying the responses of the exposure to Cd and/or Pb on the innate immune system involving NF- κ B
312 pathways would rely upon (i) an estimate of the exposure to the above-mentioned metals, (ii) the potential
313 related increase of ROS production, (iii) the activation of the NF- κ B pathway, (iv) the increase of some
314 cytokines, (v) the modulation of more general mechanisms (increase of haematopoiesis, increase of

315 neutrophils, decrease of phagocytosis activity...), and (vi) ultimately adverse outcomes such as the increase
316 of infection rate. Estimating the exposure of wildlife to contaminants in all its complexity (contaminant
317 mixtures, spatio-temporal variations, species- or stage-specificity, ecological context) is still a hard task
318 recently discussed (Morrissey et al., 2023). However, quantifying the exposure to metals and metalloids using
319 e.g. ICP methods upon invasive (internal organs such as liver or kidneys) or less invasive (blood, hair...) of a
320 species of interest along a pollution gradient is relatively efficient. Similarly, measuring ROS production (free
321 radicals such as superoxide anion or nitric oxide, non-radical ROS such as hydrogen peroxide), oxidative
322 damage (dROMS, TBARS, protein carbonyls) and enzymatic (SOD, GPx, catalase, GST, GR) and non-enzymatic
323 (OXY, GSH) anti-oxidant defences is now allowed by a number of assays that can be relatively easily performed
324 on tissues or less invasive fluids like blood (Costantini, 2022; Tanabe et al., 2022). The study of the NF- κ B
325 pathway and its three layers of regulation (activity, gene specific recruitment, cell to cell variability) is far more
326 complex in wildlife. Meier-Soelch et al. recently reviewed the concepts and the methods related to the
327 monitoring of levels of cellular NF- κ B activation states (Meier-Soelch et al., 2021). Most of these techniques
328 require high biochemical skills and appropriate lab equipment, and furthermore need cell isolation and/or
329 cell culture to take into account the high variability of NF- κ B activation state among cell types and induction
330 kinetics. Most of this might be out of reach to wildlife toxicologists, at least on a short term. The relatively
331 recent development of transcriptomic approaches in ecology and ecotoxicology, however, could bring
332 important insights into the involvement and the regulation of NF- κ B pathways in wildlife exposed to
333 pollutants. An example, if not of a true ecotoxicological study but at least of a comparison of environments
334 differing by pollution level (among other parameters), is a recent analysis of the transcriptome of rural and
335 urban great tit (*Parus major*) populations in both blood and the liver. The study revealed that the NFKBID
336 gene (coding for the protein called nuclear factor of kappa light polypeptide gene enhancer in B-cells inhibitor,
337 delta; I κ BNS) was one of the 20 most significant annotated genes that were differentially expressed between
338 urban and rural birds in whole blood transcriptomes (Watson et al., 2017). Similar RNA-sequencing analyses
339 could be performed in wildlife populations inhabiting habitats with contrasted levels of Cd and/or Pb, or in
340 individuals exposed under semi-natural controlled conditions in mesocosms. Complementarily to the random
341 search of differential expression of certain genes among exposed and non- or less-exposed populations or

342 individuals from the global transcriptomes, the present AOPs allow to specifically look for possible differential
343 expression of genes related to NF- κ B pathways. Such approach of course requires that the genes and RNAs of
344 interest have been sequenced and identified in databases, but the number of fully sequenced genomes
345 increases fast. The full genome of 1,000 species is available within the Tree of Life Programme (Wellcome
346 Sanger Institute, 2023) and overall it is estimated that the genome of more than 3,000 species has been fully
347 sequenced, with however large disparities in genomic representation (e.g. overrepresentation of vertebrates
348 over arthropods) and assembly quality (gene annotations available for 34% of the taxa, Hotaling et al., 2021).
349 To go further into the key events of the present AOPs, the potential increase of some cytokines under Cd
350 and/or Pb exposure would be required but the lack of species-specific monoclonal antibodies has historically
351 been a barrier to integrating free-ranging mammals, beyond the well-known lab model species such as lab
352 mice (*Mus musculus*) and rats (*Rattus norvegicus*). Even if the availability of reagents developed in lab mice
353 has interestingly been used to study the immunity of their wild counterparts (Abolins et al., 2018, 2017, 2011),
354 the immune system of most of wild species cannot be studied with that resolution because monoclonal
355 antibodies developed in lab mice do not (or hardly) cross-react with other rodent species, even
356 phylogenetically closed (e.g. *Apodemus sylvaticus*; Devalloir, 2023). Some cytokines and other immune
357 molecules such as immunoglobulins can however be quantified through the use of e.g. Elisa kits that
358 sometimes give satisfactory results among species (Devalloir et al., 2023). However, here again, the
359 development of full genome and transcriptome sequencing is a promising perspective as it offers the
360 opportunity to study genes or their expression rather than the proteins themselves, or produce recombinant
361 proteins for protein-based immunology in species of interest (Flies et al., 2020). Flies et al. argue for “a
362 systematic effort to develop and characterize antibodies, nanobodies, or aptamers that bind to conserved
363 protein motifs across taxonomic orders” to overcome the funding constraints limiting the development of
364 specific reagents for all species of interest (Flies et al., 2020). The study of other key events described in the
365 present AOPs such as the increase of neutrophils or the decrease of phagocytosis activity can be performed
366 by relatively classical -but usually fluid- and time-consuming- techniques such as blood smears and
367 phagocytosis assays, microbial killing assays (MKA) or whole blood microbial killing assay (WBMKA),
368 respectively (Devalloir 2023).

369 Regarding the adaptive components of the immune system, exposure to Cd or Pb has been shown to
370 decrease CD4+/CD8+ ratio and MHCII molecules expression, affecting the activation of T_H1 and T_H2 cells and
371 reducing humoral responses. T lymphocytes (T cells) are divided into two major cell types: T helper (T_H) and
372 T cytotoxic (T_C) cells. They can be distinguished by the presence of CD4 (for T_H) and CD8 (for T_C) membrane
373 glycoproteins on their surfaces. The ratio of CD4+ to CD8+ T cells is approximately 2:1 in peripheral blood of
374 healthy human and mouse, while a decreased ratio is usually an indication of immunodeficiency or
375 autoimmune disease, aging or inflammation. T cells express a unique antigen-binding receptor (T-cell
376 receptor, TCR), which recognizes processed pieces of antigen (usually peptides) bound to cell membrane
377 proteins, the MHC. Naïve CD4+ T_H cells, when they bind to an MHCII-peptide complex, become activated,
378 proliferate and differentiate into various effector T-cell subsets, mainly T helper cells (type 1 (T_H1) and type
379 17 (T_H17)), and T helper type 2 (T_H2) and T follicular (T_{FH}) cells. T_H1 and 17 regulate responses to intracellular
380 pathogens while T_H2 and T_{FH} regulate responses to extracellular pathogens such as bacteria and parasitic
381 worms. Naïve CD8+ T_C cells, when they bind to an MHCI-peptide complex, become activated, proliferate and
382 differentiate into cytotoxic T lymphocyte (CTL), which have a vital function in recognizing and eliminating cells
383 displaying non-self antigen-MHCI complex (such as virus infected or tumour cells). Further research should
384 thus also focus on cell populations, and more precisely the CD4+/CD8+ ratio, and associated major
385 histocompatibility complex (MHC) molecules (Punt, 2019). Such immunophenotyping can be done through
386 flow cytometry but this would require species-specific antibodies as anti-mouse antibodies do not or hardly
387 cross-react with immune cells from other rodent species (Devalloir, 2023; García-Mendoza et al., 2021). As
388 for some of the perspectives mentioned above, the development of antibodies that bind to conserved protein
389 motifs across taxonomic orders, if not the development of specific reagents for some species of interest, is
390 required, as we do not see how the CD4+/CD8+ ratio could be measured otherwise. Complementarily, a
391 transcriptomic approach can also be developed as it has recently been done in sheep inoculated with a
392 virulent *Anaplasma phagocytophilum* to study the temporal patterns of gene expression in response to the
393 inoculation (Eskeland et al., 2023). In the latter, however, the transcriptomic approach was completed by
394 flow-cytometry of peripheral blood mononuclear cells to further study the changes of CD4+/CD8+ ratio.

395 The putative AOPs proposed in the present articles focus mainly on sub-individual levels of organisation,
396 and perspectives of research aiming at better understanding immunotoxicological mechanisms at these levels
397 of organisation have been presented above. The AOP approach, in ecotoxicology and by extension here in
398 ecoimmunotoxicology, aims to also address effects of pollutants at higher levels of organisation. A deficient
399 immune system at the sub-individual level could lead to severe impacts on individual fitness and population
400 dynamics. The hypothesis that reduced immune function and/or increased oxidative stress in wildlife
401 chronically exposed to pollutants might increase parasite prevalence and/or loads and impact fitness has
402 poorly been investigated. It has been shown that wild rodents exhibited significant differences in the
403 functioning of their immune system compared to lab animals. (Viney and Riley, 2017) recently reviewed this
404 issue and stated that wild rodents compared to laboratory animals exhibit (i) much higher humoral (antibody)
405 responses, (ii) extensive antigenic exposure as revealed by cellular immune system, (iii) depressed
406 proliferative and cytokine responses in *ex vivo*-stimulated immune cells. Studying exposure of wildlife to
407 pathogens is increasingly accessible through *e.g.* high-throughput DNA sequencing, allowing for the
408 identification of a number of zoonotic or non-zoonotic, emerging or well-known, external or internal
409 pathogens and parasites (*e.g.*, Diagne et al., 2016; Villette et al., 2020). For assessing bacterial communities,
410 a mix of organs allows to get a better view of bacterial assemblages than single organs (Villette et al., 2017)
411 but this unfortunately requires the sacrifice of (some) individuals, which might be ethically questionable when
412 working on protected and/or endangered wildlife. The use of fluids like blood or faeces is less invasive but
413 would give a partial view of the bacterial assemblages or even false negatives as their presence in the fluids
414 depends on their distribution between organs and fluids, or on their excretion kinetics. Viruses also are
415 increasingly studied in free-ranging vertebrates (Van Brussel and Holmes, 2022; Wu et al., 2018) and non- or
416 little-invasive techniques based on faecal and oropharyngeal swabs have recently been developed (Bergner
417 et al., 2019).

418 Ecotoxicological studies often face a lack of environmental and ecological representativeness regarding
419 the overall exposure of wildlife, and how pollutants are reacting in the environmental matrix. Morrissey et al.
420 (2023) recently address this question to improve wildlife risk assessment. Indeed, the AOP framework
421 answers some of the specific guidelines they proposed (Morrissey et al., 2023). First, building AOPs allows a

422 consideration of the general chemical complexity (i.e., mixture effects, chemical properties, metabolites) of
423 pollutants. Each compound has its own mode(s) of action and pathways that lead to one or several toxic
424 effects at different levels of biological organisation. Identifying molecular initiating event(s) and key event(s)
425 that lead to adverse outcome(s) participates to understand how complex are the interactions between
426 pollutants, here Cd and Pb, in organisms. Second, once AOPs are built and the main pathways identified, it is
427 possible to make it species- or life-stages specific (i.e., considering organismal complexity; Morrissey et al.,
428 2023). This will guide the formulation of hypothesis and the choice of biomarkers. This (new) framework
429 participates in answering new questions and guide researchers into new directions in ecotoxicology, stress
430 ecology and ecoimmunotoxicology. Building AOPs before starting an experiment appears as something that
431 should become more common in these field of research to better apprehend mechanisms underlying toxic
432 effects and identify the research gaps (Baudiffier et al., 2024). In addition, developing the knowledge of the
433 database presented by Vinken et al., (2017) would encourage data sharing and literature findings to better
434 direct further research. To date, the most important limitations in making AOPs about a specific subject is the
435 lack of literature that can restrict the whole process.

436

437 **8. Conclusion**

438 Adverse outcome pathways are an efficient method to identify the mechanisms underlying the effects of
439 pollutants at various levels of biological organisation and thus, to identify research gaps in ecotoxicology and
440 risk assessment. Here, we identified potential MIEs and KEs that lead to AOs related to immune disorders in
441 mammals in response to Cd and/or Pb exposure. Cadmium and Pb may induce immuno-stimulation and
442 immunodeficiency through different pathways of the immune system, impacting both innate and adaptive
443 immune responses. Our findings could guide future research in ecoimmunotoxicology of metals. There are
444 still large open questions about how organisms, at different levels of organisation, react to pathogens and
445 infections in a context where exposure to pollutants affects immunity. Mixture effects of trace metal are also
446 still largely understudied. It is now of major importance to understand how these pollutants interact with
447 wildlife to improve conservation policies. We identified potential synergetic and antagonistic interactions

448 produced by the co-exposure to Cd and Pb, which also brings questions about the potential adaptation of
449 wild populations to those mixtures, in comparison to single-pollutant exposure.

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453 **Author contributions**

454 Conceptualization: CH, RS; Data curation: CH; Formal analysis: CH; Funding acquisition: RS; Investigation: CH;
455 Methodology: CH; Project administration: RS; Supervision: QD, NvdB, RS; Validation: CH, QD, CG, NvdB, RS;
456 Visualization: CH; Writing - original draft: CH, RS; Writing - review & editing: CH, QD, CG, NvdB, RS.

457 **Declaration of competing interest**

458 The authors declare no competing interests.

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711

1 **1. Introduction**

2 Wildlife has been threatened for decades by several stressors from anthropogenic activities, which leads
3 to the sixth mass extinction (Birnie-Gauvin et al., 2017; Ceballos et al., 2017) and makes conservation of the
4 biodiversity one of the main issues of the century. Stressors are coming from many sources, including the
5 exposure to different kinds of pollutants such as non-essential trace metals (TMs) (for readability purpose,
6 this acronym and other used in the present paper are presented in **Table 1**). Contrarily to essential elements
7 that have important physiological functions in organisms, metals such as cadmium (Cd) or lead (Pb) are non-
8 essential elements to vertebrates since they are not known to have any biological function (Aras and Ataman,
9 2007). Transfer of these toxic metals from the environment to the organisms depends on several parameters
10 regulating their bioavailability (Lanno et al., 2004), defined as the proportion of the total concentration of a
11 chemical that is actually taken up from the environment (Naidu et al., 2008). Toxicological bioavailability refers
12 to the proportion of the concentration taken up that reaches toxicological targets (e.g., cells, tissues, organs)
13 through the circulatory system, subsequently causing a biological response (Lanno et al., 2004). Historically,
14 studies on TMs have mainly focused on accumulation in tissues and effects on classical ecotoxicological
15 endpoints (mortality, reproduction outputs, histopathology, biochemical, physiological disorders...) while
16 unconventional endpoints, such as impacts on the immune system or behaviour, have attracted more
17 attention only recently. Ecoimmunotoxicology refers to the understanding of the interactions between
18 exposure to pollutants, immune cells and the “delicate interactions associated with homeostasis mediated
19 by the immune system” (Tryphonas, 2005; Gallucci et al., 2020).

20 **Table 1.**

21 Exposure to non-essential TMs at toxic levels can affect the immune system through an up-regulation
22 (immunoactivation) or a down-regulation (immunodeficiency), both referring to immunomodulation (Zelikoff
23 et al., 1994; Devalloir et al., 2023). Immunodeficiency is defined as the decrease in effectiveness of the
24 immune response (Gallucci et al., 2020) while immunostimulation refers to the enhancement of the defensive
25 response, that can lead to auto-immune dysfunction or overall immune hypersensitivity (Luster and
26 Gerberick, 2010; McKee and Fontenot, 2016; Gallucci et al., 2020). These immunomodulation processes

27 mediated by toxic metals impact both innate and adaptive responses by unsettling the balanced mechanisms
28 of immune cell regulation (Tersago et al., 2004; Ebrahimi et al., 2020). Immunomodulation is also linked to a
29 myriad of external factors and stressors such as food shortage, life stage, or exposure to pathogens (Jackson
30 et al., 2009; Poulsen and Escher, 2012). Toxic effects also vary with species, sex, type (chronic or acute) and
31 route (ingestion, inhalation, dermal contact) of exposure (Gallucci et al., 2020). Immune cell dysfunction can
32 occur through ionic substitution of toxic metals due to similar affinity to receptors on organic compounds,
33 such as Cd^{2+} crossing Ca^{2+} channels (Choong et al., 2014). The main mechanism responsible for immune cell
34 damages is related to the toxicological impact of reactive oxygen species (ROS) including immune cell
35 membrane degradation (e.g., lipopolyperoxydation, Gera et al., 2015). Cadmium and Pb also have the ability
36 to up- or down- regulate inflammatory mediators and markers (cytokines, chemokines...), which can directly
37 modify the immune response (Ebrahimi et al., 2020; Devalloir et al., 2023). Cadmium and Pb can thus induce
38 differential effects on cytokine production through different signalling pathways (Thévenod and Lee, 2015).
39 For example, an increase of the pro-inflammatory response (TNF- α) has been shown in wood mice living near
40 a former smelter site contaminated by high Cd and Pb levels (Devalloir et al., 2023).

41 Since the emergence and the development of ecotoxicology in the 60's, the discipline has evolved from a
42 relatively descriptive field to a much more mechanistic, hypothesis-based science. It aims at providing both a
43 better understanding of how pollutants can affect organisms at various spatial, temporal, and biological
44 organisation scales, and an improvement of risk assessment of chemicals released into the environment.
45 Among the approaches used in ecotoxicology to study the cascade (from molecular to population or
46 community levels) toxic effects of pollutants, adverse outcome pathways (AOPs) appeared as an innovative
47 and useful concept that could improve mechanistic approaches, here in ecoimmunotoxicology (Tryphonas,
48 2005; Baudiffier et al., 2024). Adverse outcome pathways represent a conceptual framework that highlights
49 existing knowledge linking a molecular initiating event (MIE) induced by a given toxic chemical to an adverse
50 outcome (AO) at multiple levels of biological organisation (Ankley et al., 2010). An AOP represents a
51 succession of key events (KEs) that can take various forms and depend on the information available. Molecular
52 initiating events are located at the molecular level and can be defined as “the initial points of chemical-

53 biological interaction within the organism” (Figure 1, Vinken et al., 2017). The relationship(s) between the
54 different events can be causal, mechanistic, inferential or correlation-based (Ankley et al., 2010).

55 **Figure 1.**

56 The present paper focusses on the effects of Cd and Pb on the immune system of mammals to propose
57 putative AOPs to test more mechanistic hypotheses in ecoimmunotoxicology of metals and to address future
58 questions in stress ecology (as other stressors than metals act on immunity) and ecotoxicology of free-ranging
59 mammals. Here, we focus on terrestrial mammals because reviews have recently been published on immune
60 toxicity of metals (or contaminants including metals) in fish (Lee et al., 2023, 2019), birds (Vallverdú-Coll et
61 al., 2019) and marine mammals (Desforges et al., 2016). All arsenic (As), Cd, Pb, and mercury (Hg) belong to
62 the 10 chemicals or groups of chemicals of major public health concern at a global scale (World Health
63 Organization, 2024). We however focus here on Cd and Pb only as they are more relevant than As or Hg to
64 terrestrial mammals in terms of exposure, and to keep the present article at a reasonable size. We based the
65 construction of our AOPs on reviewing the literature in the area, our own experience in ecoimmunotoxicology,
66 and different interactive databases related to AOPs. These databases provide open-source interfaces to
67 deposit AOPs, which facilitates the sharing of AOP knowledge and collaborative work (reviewed in Vinken et
68 al., 2017).

69 **2. Materials and Methods**

70 The articles presented in this paper have been selected according to the PRISMA statement (Moher et al.,
71 2009). Literature search for study cases on terrestrial mammals was performed with Web of Sciences (June
72 2023) by using the following keywords, alone or in combination, full or truncated: immune system, immunity,
73 oxidative stress, AOPs/Adverse outcomes pathways, biomarkers, mammals (wild or captive), metals/heavy
74 metals, Pb/Lead, Cd/Cadmium, mixture effects. We also included other review articles about AOPs,
75 immunology and immunotoxicity in mammals. We ended up with 123 articles after the identification phase
76 and then selected the most pertinent articles based on their title and abstract (screening phase). After the
77 eligibility phase, we finally kept 51 articles, that were included in our synthesis. After reviewing the literature
78 and building pre-AOPs, we used ~~four different~~ the AOP-wiki interactive databases (<https://aopwiki.org/>,

79 ~~e.AOP.portal, AOP-wiki, Effectopedia, and the AOP Explorer; all grouped on this link:~~
80 ~~<https://aopkb.oecd.org/index.html>,~~ Vinken et al., 2017) to expand our AOPs and link them to the existing
81 knowledge. Each KE identified in the literature was associated with a specific KE from AOP-wiki when it existed
82 (Table 2). The ~~Event ID code~~ of each KE was then added in our AOPs (see Figures). General knowledge (i.e.,
83 introduction, information about TMs) and perspectives were based on other bibliographic searches and on
84 our experience.

85 **Table 2.**

86 ~~**3. Development of an AOP for Evidence of the effects of Cd on the immune system of**~~
87 ~~**mammals based on an AOP framework**~~

88 Cadmium in the environment comes from both natural and anthropogenic sources. Primary natural source
89 of Cd is related to geological processes, such as volcanic activity (Doelsch et al., 2006). Its occurrence is natural
90 in all types of soils and minerals, e.g., sulfate, sulfide, carbonate... (Kabata-Pendias, 2010). Anthropogenic
91 sources of Cd include mining, smelting activity, transport, burial of nickel-Cd batteries, manufacturing, and
92 pesticides spreading (Hosseini-Khannazer et al., 2020). Main routes of exposure to Cd in mammals are through
93 air, water, and food intake. Cadmium enters the body *via* the respiratory and the gastrointestinal tract (Mirkov
94 et al., 2021). It is then transported into the blood, bound to some proteins such as albumin (Mirkov et al.,
95 2021) and brought to the organs where it accumulates. Overall, all the organs are targeted by Cd but its
96 accumulation is always higher in the liver and kidneys (Sarkar et al., 2013). Cells and tissues exposed to Cd
97 are mainly damaged by oxidative stress, even if reactive oxygen species (ROS) are not directly produced by
98 Cd. Reactive oxygen species are naturally produced during oxygen metabolism and are essential for cell
99 signalling and homeostasis. However, high amounts of ROS disrupt cell functioning, including immune cells,
100 and produce several adverse effects. Cadmium is considered as an immunotoxic inhibitor, influencing both
101 innate and adaptive immune responses, which can alter immune cells functions (Mirkov et al., 2021). Major
102 effects of Cd on the immune system reported in the literature are: (1) Cd-dependent apoptosis, (2) variations
103 in immune cells activation and differentiation, and (3) enhancement of inflammatory responses in immune
104 cells by up- and down-regulation of cytokines production (Genchi et al., 2020; Wang et al., 2021).

105 We identified two main MIEs for Cd, which result in significant AOs on the immune system (Figure 2). The
106 first one is linked to the chemical properties of Cd as, under its ionic form Cd²⁺, it is known to interfere with
107 essential metal ions involved in biological functions of organisms (Thévenod and Lee, 2015). Thus, Cd²⁺ can
108 block Ca²⁺ channels because of their thiol group affinity. It induces a major disturbance of cellular homeostasis
109 and affects protein structure. The second MIE is the binding of Cd on the cell surface (Choong et al., 2014).
110 Both MIEs are activating a reaction cascade of several KEs linked to immune dysfunctions.

111 The first step of this cascade is the induction of ROS production. Increase in oxidative stress affects
112 mitochondrial membranes, which plays a major role in mitochondrial ROS formation, and leads to apoptosis
113 (Genchi et al., 2020; Wang et al., 2021). Reactive oxygen species increase is responsible for the activation of
114 the NF-κB pathway, which is in turn linked to the increase of the production of the pro-inflammatory cytokines
115 IL-1b, IL-6 and TNF-α (Wang et al., 2021) and of some chemokines (IL-8, MIP-2). Enhancement of both IL-6
116 and TNF-α in neutrophils (i.e., the most abundant type of granulocytes) leads to potential indirect effects of
117 Cd on haematopoiesis because these cytokines are regulators of this mechanism (Ulich et al., 1989). It can
118 indicate a hypersensitive reaction. Bioassays using macrophages from murine cells line RAW 264.7 exposed
119 to Cd concentrations showed an increase in the pro-inflammatory cytokine IL-1β associated with an inhibition
120 of IL-6 and IL-10 (Riemschneider et al., 2015). Because of this modulation, a potential hyper-reactivity of
121 macrophages can occur, which could lead to autoimmune disorder in mammals. In addition, Jung and Oh
122 (2019) reported an increase of TNF-α 6h after an exposure to Cd, which would indicate a response from
123 macrophages to Cd toxicity. However, 18h after the exposure, a decrease in TNF-α was associated with
124 apoptosis in RAW 264.7 (So et al., 2018). These results suggest that Cd immunotoxicity varies according to
125 exposure time, resulting in a hyperactivation of the immune system during short-term exposure while long-
126 term exposure results in immunodeficiency.

127 During the regulation of oxidative stress balance, the increase of glutathione (GSH) can cause a decrease
128 in CD4+/CD8+ ratio (CD: cluster of differentiation), with a decrease of CD4+ (helper T-cells) and an increase
129 of CD8+ (cytotoxic T-cells; Devalloir et al., submitted). Moreover, a decrease in CD4+ can be linked to a
130 diminution of IL-2 and IFN-γ production (Pathak and Khandelwal, 2009). A decrease in IL-2, the main factor
131 for proliferation of activated T-cells, has been observed in mouse splenic cells after Cd exposure (Pathak and

132 Khandelwal, 2009). These results show that Cd participates to the overall inactivation and immunodeficiency
133 of the adaptive immune response in mammals. In addition, IFN- γ can be both enhanced or inhibited by Cd
134 exposure (Krocova et al., 2000; Turley et al., 2019), depending on the dose and time-exposure. Turley et al.
135 (2019) reported an enhancement of IFN- γ during low-dose Cd exposure (32 ppm in drinking water for 10 days)
136 without significantly affecting T-cell polarization in rats. On the contrary, a decrease of IFN- γ has been
137 reported in T-cells when exposed to higher Cd concentrations (Krocova et al., 2000).

138 Reactive oxygen species production also promotes the expression of some pro-inflammatory cytokines
139 such as IL-1b, IL-6 and TNF- α and inhibits anti-inflammatory cytokines such as IL-10 in macrophages (Wang et
140 al., 2021). The overexpression of IL-1b, IL-6 and TNF- α as well as the inhibition of IL-10 can result in hyper-
141 inflammation, auto immune disorders and in rare cases, cancer (Thévenod and Lee, 2015). Overall, a
142 dysregulation in cytokine production can affect the activation of TH1, Th2 or TH17 (Devalloir, 2023). In
143 addition, the binding of Cd on the cell surface induces a decrease of the expression of the major
144 histocompatibility complex class 2 (MCHII) on B-cells, which could affect the presentation of pathogens to
145 antigen presenting cells and decrease the effectiveness of the immune system in response to pathogens.
146 Antibody production is also directly affected by Cd exposure. In the spleen, B-cell antibody responses differ
147 with dose, class of antigen (IgG, IgM), antigen type (T-cell independent, T-cell dependent) and exposure
148 duration (Fujimaki et al., 1982). A decrease in IgE production has been highlighted after Cd exposure in
149 humans (Wang et al., 2021). Cadmium exposure also induces the transformation of IgE antibodies into IgG
150 produced by B lymphocytes in humans (Marth et al., 2001), indicating an impairment of the cell activation
151 initiation during cytotoxic signals (Wang et al., 2021).

152

153 **Figure 2.**

154 **3.4. Evidence of the effects of Pb on the immune system of mammals based on an AOP**
155 **framework** ~~Development of an AOP for the effects of Pb on the immune system of~~
156 ~~mammals~~

157 Lead is a naturally occurring but potentially harmful element, present at high concentrations in the
158 environment mainly because of anthropogenic sources. This element is naturally present in the earth crust at
159 very low concentration and small amount are released in the environment due to natural processes as rocks
160 weathering (Pattee and Pain, 2002). Regarding anthropogenic sources, Pb is used in paints, pesticides,
161 gasoline, batteries, and other emissions that can come from smelting activity and industry (Wani et al., 2015).
162 Main routes of exposure in mammals are through air and food intake, where it can be absorbed by respiratory
163 and digestive tracts (Balali-Mood et al., 2021). Accumulation in several organs generate multiple adverse
164 effects such as nervous system disorders (e.g., saturnism), kidney and liver alteration, anaemia, or learning
165 disorders in children (Ebrahimi et al., 2020). The oxidant-antioxidant balance system can be disturbed by Pb
166 exposure, which can lead to inflammatory responses in organs (Balali-Mood et al., 2021). Lead also is
167 considered as an immunotoxic inhibitor, influencing both innate and adaptive immune responses that can
168 alter all immune cells (Metryka et al., 2018). The major effects of Pb on the immune system reported in the
169 literature are (1) the enhancement of anti- and pro-inflammatory responses, (2) depression of humoral
170 immunity, and (3) immune cell damage at high Pb concentration.

171 Lead exposure, either chronic or acute, can induce two potential MIEs, that result in severe AOs on the
172 functioning of the immune system. First, the inhibition of δ -aminolaevulinic acid dehydratase (δ -ALA-D) by Pb
173 can lead to a rapid oxidizing of δ -ALA. Quantification of δ -ALA-D has long been used as a biomarker of Pb
174 exposure (Rocha et al., 2012). However, its use as a biomarker of Pb exposure has to be cautious because
175 modulation of δ -ALA-D can occur after an exposure to other metals. When δ -ALA-D oxidation occurs, it
176 induces a production of free radicals including ROS, leading to oxidative stress (Lopes et al., 2016). Second,
177 Pb can bind to the cell surface to oxygen compounds due to its chemical properties. Both MIEs are activating
178 a reaction cascade of several KEs linked to immune responses dysfunctions (Figure 3).

179 Innate and adaptive immune responses are both impacted by a chronic or acute Pb exposure, by producing
180 ROS, modulating cytokines production, and T_H1/T_H2 polarisation. The induction of ROS production promotes
181 or suppresses the expression of a few cytokines. Iavicoli et al. (2006) reported an increase of IL-4 and a
182 decrease of IL-2 and IFN- γ production in mice exposed to high Pb level. In comparison, low-dose Pb exposure
183 induces a decrease in IL-4, and an increase of IL-2 and IFN- γ , meaning that immune response modulation
184 might be not linear (Iavicoli et al., 2006). These responses differently affect T_H1 and T_H2 polarisation and
185 humoral responses. High Pb levels could cause an impairment of cytotoxic signalling (T_H1) while low-dose Pb
186 affects the coordination of helper T-cell response (T_H2).

187 Studies also highlighted an increase of three pro-inflammatory cytokines, IL-1 β , TNF- α and IL-6, after an
188 exposure to Pb (Fenga et al., 2017), which could promote auto-immune damage. However, antioxidant
189 activation associated with Pb exposure, in response to oxidative stress, modified pro-inflammatory responses
190 by decreasing IL-1 β , TNF- α and IL-6. Furthermore, synergistic effect between Pb and lipopolysaccharides (i.e.,
191 LPS; an inducer of inflammatory response in organisms) has been demonstrated in the literature (Cheng et
192 al., 2009). LPS-induced mortality under Pb exposure has been observed in animal studies (Dentener et al.,
193 1989) and could be due to the tremendous release of TNF- α by different cells including both T and B
194 lymphocytes, macrophages, and monocytes. In human macrophages, *in vitro* stimulation by LPS showed a
195 surface TNF- α expression on over 50% of the cells after 24h. IL-8 gene expression is also enhanced by Pb
196 exposure when associated with p42/44 MAPK in human (Lin et al., 2015). Indeed, p42/44 MAPK has been
197 observed to activate IL-8 gene expression (Metryka et al., 2018).

198 Lead also causes a decline in humoral immunity by affecting both T_H1 and T_H2, which may increase host
199 vulnerability to bacterial and virus infections (Hemphill et al., 1971; Gainer, 1974; Luster et al., 1978). Lead
200 affects humoral immune response by reducing IgA and IgG production, which can induce inflammatory
201 diseases and cancers as long-term AOs (Anetor et al., 2008). Naïve CD4⁺ exposed to Pb will preferentially
202 differentiate in T_H2 and lead to the inhibition of T_H1 cell growth. This results in a decrease of IFN- γ and IgG₂
203 with an increase of IL-4, IgE, and IgG₄. Mice exposed to Pb and infected by *Listeria monocytogenes* showed
204 significant reduction in the CD4⁺ and CD8⁺ production (Dyatlov and Lawrence, 2002).

205

206 **Figure 3.**

207 **5. Similarities and differences between Cd and Pb effects on the immune system of mammals**
208 **based on an AOP framework**

209 Overall, Cd and Pb produce similar effects in vertebrates with outcomes resulting either
210 immunostimulation or immunodeficiency. Here, we propose a single AOP (Figure 4) presenting mechanisms
211 and pathways common to the exposure to both trace metals. To our knowledge, no experiments have been
212 conducted with the very same conditions to directly compare the immunotoxicological effect of Cd and Pb.
213 This means that we cannot be sure whether the differences in the immunomodulatory effects of the exposure
214 to Cd or Pb are actual differences in the underlying mechanisms or if this is related to a lack of research.

215 Concerning the innate system, common mechanisms include tissue inflammation related to the increased
216 production of pro-inflammatory cytokines within the NF- κ B signalling pathway and a reduction of
217 phagocytosis activity. In both cases, cytokine concentrations are modulated either up or down, leading to an
218 increased inflammation or an impaired signalling of the immune response. Concerning the adaptive response,
219 both trace metals affect the expression of MHCII and produce a decrease of the CD4+/CD8+ ratio, leading to
220 an inhibition of immunoglobulin production and an impairment of Th1 and Th2 response. These various
221 common pathways all lead to three main adverse effects such as immunostimulation, potential auto-immune
222 disorder/damage, immunodeficiency leading to potential increase infection rate, and in some cases even
223 cancer.

224 Differences in immunomodulatory effects of the exposure to Cd or Pb rely mainly on one feature specific
225 to Pb (Inhibition of the δ aminolaevulinic acid dehydratase, ALA-D) and differences in cytokines mobilised
226 through exposure to Cd or Pb (see Figures 2 and 3, and text below). The inhibition of ALA-D increases oxidative
227 stress in cells (Rocha et al., 2012) but we did not find to what extent this contributes to the overall increase
228 of oxidative stress related to the exposure to Pb. Cytokines and chemokines are modulated by the exposure
229 to Cd or Pb but according to previous studies, most of them are different for each metal indicating that
230 different pathways of the immune response are involved. For example, the extra activation of NF- κ B leads to
231 increased IL-8 and MIP-2 in the case of Cd exposure while an increase of IL-4 is reported in the case of Pb

232 exposure (Iavicoli et al., 2006; Wang et al., 2021). In the case of immunoglobulin production, studies showed
233 an inhibition of IgE and an inhibition of IgA and IgG in the case of Cd and Pb, respectively (Anetor et al., 2008;
234 Wang et al., 2021).

235 **Figure 4.**

236 **4.6. Evidence of the effects of a Cd-Pb mixture on the immune system of mammals**
237 **based on an AOP framework** ~~Development of an AOP for the effects of a Cd-Pb mixture on~~
238 ~~the immune system of mammals~~

239 In the environment, organisms are generally exposed to a mixture of contaminants rather than to a single
240 trace metal. These multiple exposures can be detrimental to wild vertebrates even if contaminants are
241 present at low concentrations. This concept is called “cocktail effect” or “mixture toxicity” (Beyer et al., 2014).
242 Ecotoxicological studies have mainly been performed through a chemical-by-chemical approach of exposure,
243 while wildlife are exposed to “dynamic chemical mixtures” through their life (Morrissey et al., 2023). It exists
244 only a few papers that relate mixture effects of trace metal elements (Cd, Pb) on the immune system. ~~Overall,~~
245 ~~Cd and Pb produce similar effects in vertebrates with an outcome resulting in either an immunostimulation~~
246 ~~or an immunodeficiency. However~~ Thus, little is known about their additive, synergetic and/or antagonistic
247 effects on the immune system of vertebrates. Synergetic and antagonistic effects are the results of the
248 competition among metals for organic and inorganic ligands during accumulation and uptake (Altenburger et
249 al., 2003; Belden et al., 2007; Balistrieri and Mebane, 2014). It has been shown that Cd-Pb mixture can
250 enhance the production of white blood cells in mice, indicating the activation of the immune system in
251 response to the exposure (Cobbina et al., 2015). In addition, these authors found that the exposure to a
252 mixture result in a global antagonistic effect, in comparison to their individual toxic effect. One hypothesis
253 could be that Cd and Pb both produce thiols such as GSH, enabling a protection of the cell from their toxicity.
254 However, other antioxidant markers (superoxide dismutase, glutathione peroxidase) were lower when mice
255 were exposed to a Cd and Pb mixture, potentially creating higher oxidative stress in immune cells. Another
256 study in male rat showed that the exposure to a mixture of eight trace metals, including Cd and Pb, induces
257 a suppression of both humoral and cell-mediated immune response (Jadhav et al., 2007). Fortier et al. (2008)

258 depicted a non-significant effect of the Cd-Pb mixture in human leucocytes (viability and apoptosis
259 proportion). These few studies provide different conclusions, suggesting that a variety of pathways could be
260 involved in the response to Cd-Pb mixture. However, we still lack information about how cytokines signalling,
261 T_H1/T_H2 polarization of B-cells and antibody production could be modulated by this mixture. Here, we propose
262 a potential AOP for Cd-Pb mixture on the immune system of mammals with potential additive effects or
263 synergetic and antagonistic interactions (Figure 54), based on the few studies presented earlier as well as on
264 hypotheses and deductions from our single-chemical AOPs (Figures 2, ~~and 3~~ and 4).

265

266 **Figure 54.**

267 **5.7. Gaps in current knowledge and research perspectives**

268 In the present article, we built putative AOPs depicting the cascade effects of Cd and Pb alone, and in
269 combination, on the immune system of mammals. We identified several pathways that could lead to immune
270 dysfunctions in mammals. However, despite identifying links between contaminants, MIEs, KEs and AOs using
271 the existing knowledge, how the different cascades of reactions occur in wild organisms, and what adverse
272 outcomes arise at various levels of biological organisation remain uncertain in wildlife since most of the work
273 has been done in lab animals. To fill this gap, we identified several biomarkers indicated in bright pink boxes
274 (and indicated by an asterisk) in Figures 2 to 6, and develop hereinafter the research priority identified from
275 these putative AOPs, the literature and our own experience in immunotoxicity of metals in free-ranging small
276 mammals (Devalloir et al., 2023; Powolny et al., 2023; ongoing research).

277 One of the primary aspects to consider, common to both Cd and Pb exposure, relies upon their impacts
278 through NF-κB. This family of inducible transcription factors regulates multiple aspects of innate and adaptive
279 immune functions and is a pivotal mediator of inflammatory responses (Liu et al., 2017). NF-κB induces
280 several functions in innate immune cells, including maturation of dendritic cells, activation and differentiation
281 of inflammatory T cells, polarization of macrophages and their production of pro-inflammatory
282 cytokines/chemokines, and recruitment of and anti-apoptotic effect on neutrophils. These cells express
283 pattern-recognition receptors that detect various microbial components (so-called pathogen-associated
284 molecules patterns, PAMPs) as well as molecules released by necrotic cells and damaged tissues (co-called
285 damage-associated molecular patterns, DAMPs). Thus, a disruption of NF-κB by contaminants (here Cd or Pb)
286 could alter these functions and might lead to a lower ability of the innate immune system to fight against
287 pathogens. NF-κB also exerts a central role in mediating T cell receptors signalling and naive T-cell activation,
288 which is an important component of the adaptive immune system. Deregulation of NF-κB activation can cause
289 aberrant T-cell activation, which might lead to associated autoimmune and inflammatory responses.
290 Inflammation is a protective response of the host to infections and tissue damages and is normally beneficial
291 and resolved in a timely manner. Given that wild rodents have been shown to be particularly exposed to
292 infections, deregulation of NF-κB activation by metals might be particularly harmful to wild animals, both by

293 lowering their ability to control pathogenic infections and through excessive or long-lasting tissue damages,
294 ultimately leading to acute or chronic inflammatory diseases (Liu et al., 2017). Studying this pathway,
295 especially in free-ranging wildlife, is however difficult due to the complexity of the activation of NF- κ B, which
296 involves two major pathways (canonical and non-canonical) related to different signalling mechanisms. The
297 first pathway responds to diverse stimuli including ligands of various cytokine receptors, pattern-recognition
298 receptors (PRRs), TNF receptor (TNFR) superfamily, B and T cell receptors. In contrast, the non-canonical
299 pathway selectively responds to a specific group of stimuli, including ligands of a subset of TNFR superfamily
300 members (Liu et al., 2017). Furthermore, the activity of NF- κ B depends on three layers of regulation. A first
301 layer refers to the dynamic nature of the NF- κ B system, which is never static and is schematically under 4
302 forms of activity (OFF, low- and high-ON, and constitutively active). In “OFF” state, the NF- κ B activity is usually
303 too low to be reliably detected (Meier-Soelch et al., 2021). Constitutively active state refers to significant NF-
304 κ B activity found in specific cells such as Sertoli cells, B cells, hair follicle cells and neurons, making it difficult
305 to be studied in wildlife. “Low ON” state refers to a continuous low-grade activation that occurs in situations
306 of smoldering inflammation or in tumour microenvironment, and “high ON” state is a fast and transient
307 activation in response to proinflammatory triggers. Another layer of regulation is related to the gene specific
308 recruitment of NF- κ B and a third one involves a remarkable cell to cell variability, with cells having low NF- κ B
309 activity while adjacent cells exhibit high activity and strong activation of NF- κ B target genes (Meier-Soelch et
310 al., 2021). These authors therefore warn that (cell) population-based assays can be potentially misleading.
311 The NF- κ B activation rarely occurs in isolation and frequently other stress pathways such as p38 mitogen-
312 activated protein kinases (p38 MAPKs), c-Jun N-terminal kinases (JNKs) or JAK-STAT are activated in parallel.
313 As all have been shown to be involved in metal-related toxicity in human or lab-animal models (but not in
314 AOP framework to the best of our knowledge), they are also good candidate models to be further studied in
315 metal immunotoxicology.

316 Studying the responses of the exposure to Cd and/or Pb on the innate immune system involving NF- κ B
317 pathways would rely upon (i) an estimate of the exposure to the above-mentioned metals, (ii) the potential
318 related increase of ROS production, (iii) the activation of the NF- κ B pathway, (iv) the increase of some
319 cytokines, (v) the modulation of more general mechanisms (increase of haematopoiesis, increase of

320 neutrophils, decrease of phagocytosis activity...), and (vi) ultimately adverse outcomes such as the increase
321 of infection rate. Estimating the exposure of wildlife to contaminants in all its complexity (contaminant
322 mixtures, spatio-temporal variations, species- or stage-specificity, ecological context) is still a hard task
323 recently discussed (Morrissey et al., 2023). However, quantifying the exposure to metals and metalloids using
324 e.g. ICP methods upon invasive (internal organs such as liver or kidneys) or less invasive (blood, hair...) of a
325 species of interest along a pollution gradient is relatively efficient. Similarly, measuring ROS production (free
326 radicals such as superoxide anion or nitric oxide, non-radical ROS such as hydrogen peroxide), oxidative
327 damage (dROMS, TBARS, protein carbonyls) and enzymatic (SOD, GPx, catalase, GST, GR) and non-enzymatic
328 (OXY, GSH) anti-oxidant defences is now allowed by a number of assays that can be relatively easily performed
329 on tissues or less invasive fluids like blood (Costantini, 2022; Tanabe et al., 2022). The study of the NF-κB
330 pathway and its three layers of regulation (activity, gene specific recruitment, cell to cell variability) is far more
331 complex in wildlife. Meier-Soelch et al. recently reviewed the concepts and the methods related to the
332 monitoring of levels of cellular NF-κB activation states (Meier-Soelch et al., 2021). Most of these techniques
333 require high biochemical skills and appropriate lab equipment, and furthermore need cell isolation and/or
334 cell culture to take into account the high variability of NF-κB activation state among cell types and induction
335 kinetics. Most of this might be out of reach to wildlife toxicologists, at least on a short term. The relatively
336 recent development of transcriptomic approaches in ecology and ecotoxicology, however, could bring
337 important insights into the involvement and the regulation of NF-κB pathways in wildlife exposed to
338 pollutants. An example, if not of a true ecotoxicological study but at least of a comparison of environments
339 differing by pollution level (among other parameters), is a recent analysis of the transcriptome of rural and
340 urban great tit (*Parus major*) populations in both blood and the liver. The study revealed that the NFKBID
341 gene (coding for the protein called nuclear factor of kappa light polypeptide gene enhancer in B-cells inhibitor,
342 delta; IκBNS) was one of the 20 most significant annotated genes that were differentially expressed between
343 urban and rural birds in whole blood transcriptomes (Watson et al., 2017). Similar RNA-sequencing analyses
344 could be performed in wildlife populations inhabiting habitats with contrasted levels of Cd and/or Pb, or in
345 individuals exposed under semi-natural controlled conditions in mesocosms. Complementarily to the random
346 search of differential expression of certain genes among exposed and non- or less-exposed populations or

347 individuals from the global transcriptomes, the present AOPs allow to specifically look for possible differential
348 expression of genes related to NF- κ B pathways. Such approach of course requires that the genes and RNAs of
349 interest have been sequenced and identified in databases, but the number of fully sequenced genomes
350 increases fast. The full genome of 1,000 species is available within the Tree of Life Programme (Wellcome
351 Sanger Institute, 2023) and overall it is estimated that the genome of more than 3,000 species has been fully
352 sequenced, with however large disparities in genomic representation (e.g. overrepresentation of vertebrates
353 over arthropods) and assembly quality (gene annotations available for 34% of the taxa, Hotaling et al., 2021).
354 To go further into the key events of the present AOPs, the potential increase of some cytokines under Cd
355 and/or Pb exposure would be required but the lack of species-specific monoclonal antibodies has historically
356 been a barrier to integrating free-ranging mammals, beyond the well-known lab model species such as lab
357 mice (*Mus musculus*) and rats (*Rattus norvegicus*). Even if the availability of reagents developed in lab mice
358 has interestingly been used to study the immunity of their wild counterparts (Abolins et al., 2018, 2017, 2011),
359 the immune system of most of wild species cannot be studied with that resolution because monoclonal
360 antibodies developed in lab mice do not (or hardly) cross-react with other rodent species, even
361 phylogenetically closed (e.g. *Apodemus sylvaticus*; Devalloir, 2023). Some cytokines and other immune
362 molecules such as immunoglobulins can however be quantified through the use of e.g. Elisa kits that
363 sometimes give satisfactory results among species (Devalloir et al., 2023). However, here again, the
364 development of full genome and transcriptome sequencing is a promising perspective as it offers the
365 opportunity to study genes or their expression rather than the proteins themselves, or produce recombinant
366 proteins for protein-based immunology in species of interest (Flies et al., 2020). Flies et al. argue for “a
367 systematic effort to develop and characterize antibodies, nanobodies, or aptamers that bind to conserved
368 protein motifs across taxonomic orders” to overcome the funding constraints limiting the development of
369 specific reagents for all species of interest (Flies et al., 2020). The study of other key events described in the
370 present AOPs such as the increase of neutrophils or the decrease of phagocytosis activity can be performed
371 by relatively classical -but usually fluid- and time-consuming- techniques such as blood smears and
372 phagocytosis assays, microbial killing assays (MKA) or whole blood microbial killing assay (WBMKA),
373 respectively (Devalloir 2023).

374 Regarding the adaptive components of the immune system, exposure to Cd or Pb has been shown to
375 decrease CD4+/CD8+ ratio and MHCII molecules expression, affecting the activation of T_H1 and T_H2 cells and
376 reducing humoral responses. T lymphocytes (T cells) are divided into two major cell types: T helper (T_H) and
377 T cytotoxic (T_C) cells. They can be distinguished by the presence of CD4 (for T_H) and CD8 (for T_C) membrane
378 glycoproteins on their surfaces. The ratio of CD4+ to CD8+ T cells is approximately 2:1 in peripheral blood of
379 healthy human and mouse, while a decreased ratio is usually an indication of immunodeficiency or
380 autoimmune disease, aging or inflammation. T cells express a unique antigen-binding receptor (T-cell
381 receptor, TCR), which recognizes processed pieces of antigen (usually peptides) bound to cell membrane
382 proteins, the MHC. Naïve CD4+ T_H cells, when they bind to an MHCII-peptide complex, become activated,
383 proliferate and differentiate into various effector T-cell subsets, mainly T helper cells (type 1 (T_H1) and type
384 17 (T_H17)), and T helper type 2 (T_H2) and T follicular (T_{FH}) cells. T_H1 and 17 regulate responses to intracellular
385 pathogens while T_H2 and T_{FH} regulate responses to extracellular pathogens such as bacteria and parasitic
386 worms. Naïve CD8+ T_C cells, when they bind to an MHCI-peptide complex, become activated, proliferate and
387 differentiate into cytotoxic T lymphocyte (CTL), which have a vital function in recognizing and eliminating cells
388 displaying non-self antigen-MHCI complex (such as virus infected or tumour cells). Further research should
389 thus also focus on cell populations, and more precisely the CD4+/CD8+ ratio, and associated major
390 histocompatibility complex (MHC) molecules (Punt, 2019). Such immunophenotyping can be done through
391 flow cytometry but this would require species-specific antibodies as anti-mouse antibodies do not or hardly
392 cross-react with immune cells from other rodent species (Devalloir, 2023; García-Mendoza et al., 2021). As
393 for some of the perspectives mentioned above, the development of antibodies that bind to conserved protein
394 motifs across taxonomic orders, if not the development of specific reagents for some species of interest, is
395 required, as we do not see how the CD4+/CD8+ ratio could be measured otherwise. Complementarily, a
396 transcriptomic approach can also be developed as it has recently been done in sheep inoculated with a
397 virulent *Anaplasma phagocytophilum* to study the temporal patterns of gene expression in response to the
398 inoculation (Eskeland et al., 2023). In the latter, however, the transcriptomic approach was completed by
399 flow-cytometry of peripheral blood mononuclear cells to further study the changes of CD4+/CD8+ ratio.

400 The putative AOPs proposed in the present articles focus mainly on sub-individual levels of organisation,
401 and perspectives of research aiming at better understanding immunotoxicological mechanisms at these levels
402 of organisation have been presented above. The AOP approach, in ecotoxicology and by extension here in
403 ecoimmunotoxicology, aims to also address effects of pollutants at higher levels of organisation. A deficient
404 immune system at the sub-individual level could lead to severe impacts on individual fitness and population
405 dynamics. The hypothesis that reduced immune function and/or increased oxidative stress in wildlife
406 chronically exposed to pollutants might increase parasite prevalence and/or loads and impact fitness has
407 poorly been investigated. It has been shown that wild rodents exhibited significant differences in the
408 functioning of their immune system compared to lab animals. (Viney and Riley, 2017) recently reviewed this
409 issue and stated that wild rodents compared to laboratory animals exhibit (i) much higher humoral (antibody)
410 responses, (ii) extensive antigenic exposure as revealed by cellular immune system, (iii) depressed
411 proliferative and cytokine responses in *ex vivo*-stimulated immune cells. Studying exposure of wildlife to
412 pathogens is increasingly accessible through *e.g.* high-throughput DNA sequencing, allowing for the
413 identification of a number of zoonotic or non-zoonotic, emerging or well-known, external or internal
414 pathogens and parasites (*e.g.*, Diagne et al., 2016; Villette et al., 2020). For assessing bacterial communities,
415 a mix of organs allows to get a better view of bacterial assemblages than single organs (Villette et al., 2017)
416 but this unfortunately requires the sacrifice of (some) individuals, which might be ethically questionable when
417 working on protected and/or endangered wildlife. The use of fluids like blood or faeces is less invasive but
418 would give a partial view of the bacterial assemblages or even false negatives as their presence in the fluids
419 depends on their distribution between organs and fluids, or on their excretion kinetics. Viruses also are
420 increasingly studied in free-ranging vertebrates (Van Brussel and Holmes, 2022; Wu et al., 2018) and non- or
421 little-invasive techniques based on faecal and oropharyngeal swabs have recently been developed (Bergner
422 et al., 2019).

423 Ecotoxicological studies often face a lack of environmental and ecological representativeness regarding
424 the overall exposure of wildlife, and how pollutants are reacting in the environmental matrix. Morrissey et al.
425 (2023) recently address this question to improve wildlife risk assessment. Indeed, the AOP framework
426 answers some of the specific guidelines they proposed (Morrissey et al., 2023). First, building AOPs allows a

427 consideration of the general chemical complexity (i.e., mixture effects, chemical properties, metabolites) of
428 pollutants. Each compound has its own mode(s) of action and pathways that lead to one or several toxic
429 effects at different levels of biological organisation. Identifying molecular initiating event(s) and key event(s)
430 that lead to adverse outcome(s) participates to understand how complex are the interactions between
431 pollutants, here Cd and Pb, in organisms. Second, once AOPs are built and the main pathways identified, it is
432 possible to make it species- or life-stages specific (i.e., considering organismal complexity; Morrissey et al.,
433 2023). This will guide the formulation of hypothesis and the choice of biomarkers. This (new) framework
434 participates in answering new questions and guide researchers into new directions in ecotoxicology, stress
435 ecology and ecoimmunotoxicology. Building AOPs before starting an experiment appears as something that
436 should become more common in these field of research to better apprehend mechanisms underlying toxic
437 effects and identify the research gaps (Baudiffier et al., 2024). In addition, developing the knowledge of the
438 database presented by Vinken et al., (2017) would encourage data sharing and literature findings to better
439 direct further research. To date, the most important limitations in making AOPs about a specific subject is the
440 lack of literature that can restrict the whole process.

441

442 **6.8. Conclusion**

443 Adverse outcome pathways are an efficient method to identify the mechanisms underlying the effects of
444 pollutants at various levels of biological organisation and thus, to identify research gaps in ecotoxicology and
445 risk assessment. Here, we identified potential MIEs and KEs that lead to AOs related to immune disorders in
446 mammals in response to Cd and/or Pb exposure. Cadmium and Pb may induce immuno-stimulation and
447 immunodeficiency through different pathways of the immune system, impacting both innate and adaptive
448 immune responses. Our findings could guide future research in ecoimmunotoxicology of metals. There are
449 still large open questions about how organisms, at different levels of organisation, react to pathogens and
450 infections in a context where exposure to pollutants affects immunity. Mixture effects of trace metal are also
451 still largely understudied. It is now of major importance to understand how these pollutants interact with
452 wildlife to improve conservation policies. We identified potential synergetic and antagonistic interactions

453 produced by the co-exposure to Cd and Pb, which also brings questions about the potential adaptation of
454 wild populations to those mixtures, in comparison to single-pollutant exposure.

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458 **Author contributions**

459 Conceptualization: CH, RS; Data curation: CH; Formal analysis: CH; Funding acquisition: RS; Investigation: CH;
460 Methodology: CH; Project administration: RS; Supervision: QD, NvdB, RS; Validation: CH, QD, CG, NvdB, RS;
461 Visualization: CH; Writing - original draft: CH, RS; Writing - review & editing: CH, QD, CG, NvdB, RS.

462 **Declaration of competing interest**

463 The authors declare no competing interests.

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716

1 **Table 1.** Abbreviations used in the present article.

AO(s)	Adverse Outcome(s)	MCHII	Major Histocompatibility Complex II
AOP(s)	Adverse Outcome Pathway(s)	MIE(s)	Molecular Initiating Event(s)
Ab	Antibody	MIP-2	Macrophage Inflammatory Protein 2
Ca	Calcium	NF-κB	Nuclear Factor Kappa B
Cd	Cadmium	Pb	Lead
GSH	Glutathione	MAPK	Mitogen-Activated Protein Kinase
IFN-γ	Interferon-γ	ROS	Reactive Oxygen Species
Ig	Immunoglobulin	TNF-α	Tumour Necrosis Factor-α
IL	Interleukin	TM(s)	Trace Metal(s)
KE(s)	Key Event(s)	δ-ALA	δ-AminoLevulinic Acid
LPS	Lipopolysaccharide	δ-ALA-D	δ-Aminolevulinic Acid Dehydratase

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4 **Table 2.** Key-events found in the AOP-wiki database in relation to the AOPs developed in the present article.
5 Individual Event ID are indicated in each associated box of the AOPs (see Figures). The last column contains
6 the ID of the other AOPs from the AOP-wiki database that include the different key events of our own AOPs.

Event ID	KE name	Biological level	Other AOPs
1238	Activation of oxidative stress pathway	Molecular	
1969	Increase, Oxidative Stress	Molecular	437/457/459/507/509/510/511
1770	Decrease, Mitochondrial membrane potential	Cellular	328/387/447
1262	Apoptosis	Cellular	205/207/212/285/419/439/452/ 393/476/460/500/491/502
1365	Increase, Apoptosis	Cellular	322/331/330/325/326/441/444/509
1172	Increased activation, Nuclear factor kappa B (NF-κB)	Cellular	382/377/319/443
130	Depletion, GSH	Cellular	492
151	Activation, Inflammatory cytokines, chemokines, cytoprotective gene pathways	Molecular	
1020	Suppression, IL-2 and IL-4 production	Cellular	154
1225	Immune system inflammation	Tissue	
1750	Increased inflammatory immune responses	Tissue	320/426
149	Increase, Inflammation	Cellular/Tissue	27/115/206/280/439/505
1569	Impaired T cell activation	Cellular	
1702	Suppression of T cell activation	Cellular	227
1644	Impaired Ab production	Cellular	
403	Suppression, Immune system	Individual	14/84/85/432

7

1 **Figure 1.** Generic AOPs structure for a single chemical, that can be applied to any organism and spread for
2 different biological organisations (adapted from Vinken et al., 2017). MIE stands for molecular initiating
3 events, KE for key events and AO for adverse outcome.

7 **Figure 2.** Representation of an adverse outcome pathway for cadmium toxicity on the mammal immune
 8 system. As in Figure 1, the chemical initiator is represented in orange, molecular initiating events in green,
 9 key events in pink and adverse outcomes in red. Bright pink (also indicated with a black star) key events are
 10 potential biomarkers that could be used in future applied studies. The M and N abbreviations above some
 11 boxes stand for macrophages and neutrophils, respectively. Numerical Event ID next to the different
 12 components of the AOP are from <https://aopwiki.org/>, and are also presented in Table 1.

13 *The modulation of TNF- α vary depending on cadmium exposure time. Acute exposure result in an increase
 14 of its production while a longer exposure time resulted in a decrease of TNF- α .

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23 **Figure 3.** Representation of an adverse outcome pathway for lead toxicity on the mammal immune system.
 24 The chemical initiator is represented in orange, molecular initiating events in green, key events in pink and
 25 adverse outcomes in red. Bright pink (also indicated with a black star) key events are potential biomarkers
 26 that could be used in future applied studies. The M and N abbreviations above some boxes stand for
 27 macrophages and neutrophils, respectively. The dotted arrows indicate that the link between two events is
 28 not precisely detailed in the literature. Numerical Event ID next to the different components of the AOP are
 29 from <https://aopwiki.org/>, and are also presented in Table 1.

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33 **Figure 4.** Representation of an adverse outcome pathway for both lead and cadmium toxicity on the mammal
 34 immune system. The molecular initiating events are represented in green, key events in pink and adverse
 35 outcomes in red. Bright pink (also indicated with a black star) key events are potential biomarkers that could
 36 be used in future applied studies. The dotted arrows indicate that the link between two events is not precisely
 37 detailed in the literature. Numerical Event ID next to the different components of the AOP are from
 38 <https://aopwiki.org/>, and are also presented in Table 1.

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41 **Figure 5.** Representation of an adverse outcome pathway of the mixture of cadmium and lead toxicity on the
 42 mammal immune system. The chemical initiator is represented in orange, molecular initiating events in green,
 43 key events in pink and adverse outcomes in red. Bright pink key events (also indicated with a black star)
 44 are potential biomarkers that could be used in future applied studies. (=) are for additive interaction, (+) are for
 45 synergetic interaction, and (-) are for antagonistic interaction. Numerical Event ID next to the different
 46 components of the AOP are from <https://aopwiki.org/>, and are also presented in Table 1.

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Declaration of interests

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: